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CICLO XXXVII

**Advanced Bidirectional Three-Phase
Power Factor correctors (PFC)
for DC Microgrids**

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Contents

Contents	ii
List of Figures	vii
List of Tables	xiii
Abstract	xv
	xix
Acknowledgements	xxi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background and Motivations	1
1.2 Challenges and Research Gaps of Existing Three-Phase PFC Converters in dc Microgrid applications	3
1.2.1 Standardization of dc Microgrids Voltage Level	3
1.2.2 Grounding of dc Microgrids	5
1.2.3 Increased Penetration of Grid-Interfacing Converters in Future Power Systems	6
1.3 Main Objectives	7
1.4 Dissertation Outline	7
1.5 Main Contributions	8
1.6 List of publications	10
2 Comparative Evaluation of Three-phase Single-stage Bidirectional Converters for Interfacing the AC Grid with the DC Microgrid	13
2.1 Introduction and Background	13
2.2 Topology Overview	16
2.2.1 Y-Converter	16
2.2.2 Seven-Switch Buck Converter	18
2.2.3 Swiss Converter	19
2.3 Analytical Power Loss Model	19
2.3.1 Semiconductor Conduction Losses	22
2.3.2 Semiconductors Switching Losses	22
2.3.3 Inductor Losses:	24

2.4	Comparative Evaluation	26
2.4.1	Semiconductors Stresses	26
2.4.1.1	Voltage Stresses	26
2.4.1.2	Current Stresses	27
2.4.2	Semiconductors Losses	28
2.4.2.1	Conduction Losses	28
2.4.2.2	Switching Losses	30
2.4.3	Inductor Losses	30
2.5	Experimental Results	30
2.5.1	Key Waveforms and AC Current THDs	30
2.5.2	Measured Efficiency and Power Loss Breakdown	31
2.6	Conclusion	34
3	Four-wire Y-converter for an Enhanced Interlinking in Hybrid Microgrids	35
3.1	Introduction and Background	35
3.2	Analysis of the Proposed Converter	40
3.3	Topology Evaluation	45
3.3.1	Semiconductor Devices Evaluation	45
3.3.2	Magnetic Elements Evaluation	48
3.4	Control and Modulation	49
3.4.1	Grid-following Mode	50
3.4.2	Islanded Mode	52
3.5	Simulation Results	53
3.5.1	Balanced AC Grid Conditions	53
3.5.2	Unbalanced AC Grid Conditions	54
3.5.3	Disconnection of a Single Module	55
3.5.4	Islanded Operation	55
3.6	Experimental Results	55
3.6.1	Balanced AC Grid Conditions	56
3.6.2	Unbalanced AC Grid Conditions	57
3.6.3	Disconnection of a Single Module	59
3.6.4	Islanded Operation	60
3.7	Conclusion	61
4	Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC Systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid	63
4.1	Introduction and Background	63
4.1.1	Multiport Interlinking Converters: Motivations and Structures	64
4.1.2	Proposed Converter	67
4.2	Proposed Multiport Y-converter	68
4.2.1	Derivation and Operation Principle	68
4.2.2	Analysis and Fundamental Relations	70
4.2.2.1	Buck Mode	70
4.2.2.2	Boost Mode	72

4.3	Topology Evaluation for Wide-range of DC Ports Voltage	73
4.3.1	Semiconductor devices stresses	74
4.3.1.1	Voltage stresses	74
4.3.1.2	Current stresses	74
4.3.2	Semiconductor devices losses	76
4.4	Topology Comparison and Evaluation	78
4.4.1	Evaluation of the Proposed converter against two Y-converters	78
4.4.2	Evaluation of the Proposed converter against the DC-link coupled MPC using VSC and IBs	81
4.4.2.1	VSC+IBs	81
4.4.2.2	Topology Comparison and Evaluation	81
4.4.2.3	Semiconductor Devices	83
4.4.2.4	Magnetic Elements	85
4.5	Control and Modulation	88
4.6	Simulation results	90
4.7	Experimental Results	91
4.8	Conclusion	97
5	Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC Systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid	99
5.1	Introduction and Background	99
5.2	Principle of Operation and Analysis	101
5.2.1	Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)	102
5.2.2	Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)	104
5.3	Minimization of the Low-frequency Voltage Ripples at the DC ports	107
5.4	Simulation Results	109
5.5	Experimental Results	111
5.5.1	Steady-State Experimental Results	114
5.5.1.1	Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)	116
5.5.1.2	Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)	118
5.5.2	Transient Experimental Results	120
5.5.2.1	Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)	120
5.5.2.2	Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)	123
5.5.3	Efficiency Evaluation	125
5.5.3.1	Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)	126
5.5.3.2	Mode II ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)	129
5.6	Conclusion	129
6	Conclusions and Future Work	131
6.1	Conclusions	131
6.2	Future work	132

Bibliography

135

List of Figures

1.1	Example of dc microgrids in residential applications.	2
1.2	Example of dc microgrids in industrial applications.	3
1.3	Different nominal voltages and voltage bands of LV dc systems, along with their corresponding shares based on documented use cases.	4
1.4	DC voltage range of both three-phase buck and boost PFC converters as a function of the ac grid line-to-line rms voltage.	5
1.5	Representation of a Multiport converter interfacing various sources, loads and storages.	6
2.1	A bidirectional DC/AC converter connecting a DC microgrid to an AC grid.	14
2.2	Schematic of the isolated Y-converter	15
2.3	The three buck-type converters. (a) Y-converter; (b) seven-switch converter; and (c) Swiss converter.	17
2.4	Modulation techniques for the three topologies. (a) Y-converter; (b) seven-switch converter; and (c) Swiss converter.	20
2.5	The stresses of the different semiconductor devices in the three topologies.	23
2.6	Summation of the squared RMS currents of semiconductor devices of the studied topologies.	27
2.7	Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the number of semiconductors, semiconductor stresses and losses, the size of the heat sink, and the magnetic element sizes.	29
2.8	Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the semiconductor losses across the entire power operation range. Subfigures (a), (b), and (c) depict different loss components: conduction losses, switching losses, and semiconductor losses, respectively.	31
2.9	Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the inductor losses across the entire power operation range.	32
2.10	Picture of the Y-converter prototype.	32
2.11	Key waveforms of the rectification mode at rated power.	33
2.12	Key waveforms of the inversion mode at rated power.	33
2.13	Measured efficiency of the prototype.	33
2.14	Loss Breakdown.	34

3.1	A bidirectional converter connecting a DC MG to an AC MG in hybrid MG	36
3.2	A schematic of the proposed four-wire modular converter	40
3.3	Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter include current paths in both buck and boost modes	42
3.4	Basic waveforms of the four-wire modular converter	44
3.5	Comparison of the proposed converter with the 4-leg VSC + buck in terms of semiconductor and magnetic devices.	47
3.6	Block diagram of the control structure for the proposed converter	50
3.7	Simulation results for balanced conditions	53
3.8	Different current control strategies under unbalanced conditions	54
3.9	fault tolerant operation under one module disconnection	55
3.10	Experimental prototype of the proposed converter	56
3.11	Experimental results under balanced AC grid: (a) Rectification mode at rated power, (b) Inversion mode at rated power, and (c) Efficiency curve of the experimental prototype	58
3.12	Experimental results under balanced AC grid with step changes in the load: (a) Step change in rectification mode from 50% to 100% of rated power, (b) Step change from rectification to inversion mode.	59
3.13	Experimental waveforms under unbalanced AC grid with different current control techniques: (a) Constant input resistance mode at rated power, (b) Constant input current mode at rated power, and (c) Constant input power mode at rated power	60
3.14	Experimental waveforms to demonstrate the fault tolerant operation under one module disconnection	61
3.15	Experimental waveforms of islanded mode: (a) Balanced load, (b) Unbalanced load	62
4.1	Integration of two dc MGs with the ac grid: (a) Utilizing two-port converters; (b) Utilizing a Multiport converter.	64
4.2	Different MPC structures for interfacing dc systems with the ac grid: (a) dc-coupled MPCs; (b) Magnetically-coupled MPCs; (c) Modified MPC structures.	66
4.3	A schematic of two-port and multiport Y-converters in a modular form: (a) Two-port Y-converter; (b) The proposed Multiport Y-converter.	68
4.4	Module <i>a</i> of the proposed converter.	69
4.5	Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter: (a) Buck mode when $v_{am} > V_{dc1}$; (b) Boost mode when $v_{am} < V_{dc1}$	71
4.6	Key waveforms of module <i>a</i> of the proposed converter.	73
4.7	Fitted contour plots illustrating the RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.	75
4.8	Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.	77

4.9	Evaluation of the semiconductor losses using PLECS: (a) For two Y-converters at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (b) Semiconductor losses breakdown of two Y-converters at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2} ; (c) For the proposed converter at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (b) Semiconductor losses breakdown of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2}	80
4.10	Schematic and key waveforms of the VSC+IBs.	82
4.11	Evaluation of both converters in terms of semiconductor stresses and chip area.	84
4.12	Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.	86
4.13	Evaluation of converters in terms of inductors volume.	88
4.14	A detailed block diagram illustrating the control structure of the proposed converter: (a) The overall block diagram of the proposed control structure; (b) A detailed description of current controller 1 block; (c) A detailed description of current controller 2 block; (d) A detailed description of Bu_x modulators; (e) A detailed description of Bo_{x1} modulators; and (f) A detailed description of Bo_{x2} modulators.	89
4.15	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.	92
4.16	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 0 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.	93
4.17	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to -5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.	94
4.18	Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter.	95
4.19	Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 360 V and 400 V under different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} : (a) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW; (b) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 3 kW and 0 kW, respectively; (c) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 3 kW and -3 kW, respectively; and (d) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to -3 kW and -3 kW, respectively.	96
4.20	Calculated losses breakdown of the experimental prototype at P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW.	97
4.21	Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the experimental prototype: (a) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} increased from 0.3 kW to 3 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} decreased from 3 kW to 0.3 kW; (c) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} changed from 3 kW to -3 kW; (d) P_{dc1} equal to -3 kW and P_{dc2} changed from -0.3 kW to -3 kW.	98
5.1	Interfacing two dc systems with the ac grid: (a) Employing two converters - a single-phase and a three-phase bidirectional converter based on the dc microgrid power level; and (b) Employing a multi-port converter.	100

5.2	Different configurations of the modular Y-converter: (a) The two-port Y-converter, (b) The symmetric multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC), and (c) The asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC).	102
5.3	Key waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC in different operating modes: (a) Mode I: when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} and (b) Mode II: when V_{dc1} is greater than V_{dc2} .	105
5.4	Different waveforms of $i_{La2_{av}}$ to be analyzed for reducing the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports: (a) original waveform; (b) dc waveform; (c) ideal waveform eliminating the low-frequency voltage ripples; and (d) clamped waveform. The waveforms are not to scale.	108
5.5	Different waveforms of i_{La2} and their corresponding i_{La1} to maintain balanced ac grid currents: (a) i_{La2} original waveform; (b) i_{La2} dc waveform; and (c) i_{La2} clamped waveform.	110
5.6	Required C_{dc2} for the three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms with V_{dc1} is fixed at 400 V, P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW and 1 kW, respectively.	111
5.7	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 0 kW.	112
5.8	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 1 kW.	113
5.9	Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 3 kW.	114
5.10	Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter highlighting the implemented ac-side half-bridge modules.	115
5.11	Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.	117
5.12	Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.	118
5.13	Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the clamped $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.	119
5.14	Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode II, using the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.	120

- 5.15 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW. 121
- 5.16 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW. 122
- 5.17 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW. 122
- 5.18 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW. 123
- 5.19 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the clamped $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW. 124
- 5.20 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the clamped $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW. 124
- 5.21 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode II with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW. 125
- 5.22 Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW. 126
- 5.23 Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V. 127
- 5.24 Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V. 127

5.25	Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the clamped i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V.	128
5.26	Efficiency comparison of the proposed converter in Mode I with different i_{L2av} waveforms. The efficiency is evaluated across a range of P_{dc1} values at P_{dc2} equals 1 kW, V_{dc1} equals 400 V, and V_{dc2} equals 500 V.	128
5.27	Efficiency comparison of the proposed converter in Mode I with different i_{L2av} waveforms. The efficiency is evaluated across a range of P_{dc2} values at P_{dc1} equals 3 kW, V_{dc1} equals 400 V, and V_{dc2} equals 500 V.	129
5.28	Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode II with the original i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 500 V, V_{dc2} equals 400 V.	130

List of Tables

2.1	Three-phase PFC rectifier parameters utilized in both the evaluation of the converters and the experimental prototype.	21
2.2	Inductor parameters.	26
3.1	Summary of the different topologies proposed in the literature for interlinking converters (ILCs), highlighting the key differences between the topologies, as well as the key motivations and challenges of each	38
3.2	Basic equations of the proposed converter for module a	43
3.3	Specifications utilized in converters evaluation	45
3.4	Main components utilized in the experimental prototype	56
4.1	Summary of the basic equations of the proposed converter.	72
4.2	Parameters of the proposed converter	74
4.3	Parameters of the proposed converter.	78
4.4	Specifications utilized in converters evaluation	83
4.5	Selected SiC devices for converters evaluation	84
4.6	Parameters of the PI controllers adopted in the current control loops.	90
4.7	SiC devices and passive components utilized in the experimental prototype.	95
5.1	Summary of the basic equations of the proposed converter.	107
5.2	Parameters of the proposed converter	110

Abstract

DC microgrids represent a pivotal advancement in power distribution, offering superior efficiency and control over traditional ac systems. Key technologies such as renewable energy sources, energy storage systems, and electric vehicles operate natively on dc, significantly reducing the need for costly and energy-intensive ac-dc conversions.

To enable the coexistence of dc microgrids with conventional ac grids, hybrid energy architectures are emerging as a viable solution. These hybrid networks facilitate seamless power exchange between centralized power plants and decentralized renewable energy sources, allowing each system to operate under optimal conditions. Power Factor Correction (PFC) converters are essential in this integration process. By managing the interface between ac and dc systems, PFC converters ensure efficient bidirectional power flow—allowing dc microgrids to export power to the ac grid and vice versa—while maintaining high power quality across both domains.

This dissertation focuses on the development of PFC converter topologies aimed at enhancing the interlinking between ac grids and dc microgrids. The primary objective is to propose novel converter topologies that enable a more efficient, compact, flexible, and reliable interface between ac and dc systems. Given the strong potential of the 400 V dc system for future dc microgrids, particularly in residential and commercial applications, buck-type PFC converters are the primary focus of this work. Additionally, buck-boost PFC converters are explored to extend the capability of interfacing with a wider range of dc systems.

The research activities begin with a comparative evaluation of bidirectional single-stage non-isolated buck-type topologies. A wide range of converters is studied and analyzed, with the Y-converter, seven-switch converter, and Swiss converter selected for detailed evaluation due to their potential superior performance. The evaluation criteria include the number of semiconductors, semiconductor stresses and losses, magnetic component sizes and losses, and heat sink size.

This evaluation is conducted using an analytical power loss model and PLECS simulations. The results indicate that the Y-converter offers superior overall performance compared to the other topologies, making it a promising candidate for this application. A 10 kW prototype of the Y-converter is then constructed, demonstrating a peak efficiency of 99.26% and an efficiency of 97.47% at rated output power.

Building on the motivations for the Y-converter, a modified three-phase four-wire bidirectional topology, named the Four-wire Y-converter, is proposed. This configuration incorporates the ac grid's neutral by directly connecting it to the positive terminal of the dc microgrid. The inclusion of the neutral wire enables islanded operation of the hybrid microgrid, ensuring a stable power supply for both single-phase and three-phase ac loads. Additionally, the direct connection between the ac microgrid neutral and the dc microgrid's positive terminal allows for grounding of both microgrids, a feature previously achievable only with isolated topologies. The Four-wire Y-converter also demonstrates control over positive, negative, and zero sequence components, providing flexibility under ac voltage imbalances to ensure optimal performance. Furthermore, the converter allows for independent phase control, enabling fault-tolerant operation, which is validated under single-phase fault conditions. The converter's performance is thoroughly assessed through experimental testing on a 7 kW prototype under various conditions, including balanced and unbalanced ac voltages, single-module disconnection, and islanded operation.

The scope of the research transitions from two-port converters to multiport converters, driven by the rising popularity of dc systems and the corresponding demand for advanced power converters. Multiport converters (MPCs) have emerged as promising and efficient solutions by integrating multiple energy ports into a single hub, providing a streamlined and potentially cost-effective approach. A single-stage non-isolated multiport converter, named the Multiport Y-converter, is proposed to interface the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. When applied in 400 V dc microgrids, the proposed converter enables direct power sharing between dc microgrids, reducing dependence on the ac grid while enhancing both the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface compared to using multiple two-port converters.

The key motivations for the Multiport Y-converter include its single-stage power conversion across multiple ports, which improves efficiency and power density. The absence of bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and transformers further reduces cost and size. Additionally, the converter features buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the dc ports' voltage

levels, providing flexibility to interface with a wide range of dc systems. The topology is evaluated for dc port voltages ranging from 350 V to 800 V. To highlight the superior performance of the proposed converter, a comprehensive comparison is conducted against two Y-converter topologies and a dc-link coupled multiport converter. The performance of the Multiport Y-converter is validated through experimental testing under various operating conditions.

Lastly, another single-stage non-isolated multiport converter, named the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, is proposed to interface the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. The Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter features a more compact structure compared to the Multiport Y-converter, potentially leading to a lower-cost power converter, particularly when interfacing two dc ports with differing power levels. Challenges inherent to the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, such as maintaining balanced ac grid currents due to its asymmetric design and minimizing low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports, are addressed with proposed solutions. The converter's performance is validated through experimental tests under various operating conditions, including steady-state and transient results, as well as efficiency evaluations.

To my father,

The foundation of who I am today. Thank you for your unwavering support and constant care.

To my mother,

I wish you were here with me. You are the first and most cherished woman in my life. May Allah unite us in His eternal paradise.

To my wife,

Thank you for your love and for being my guiding light during my darkest days. May Allah bless our son, Adam, and our marriage.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivations

DC microgrids are localized grid systems that utilize direct current for power distribution, offering a more streamlined and efficient architecture for modern technological applications compared to traditional ac systems [1–3]. Key technologies, such as renewable energy sources (RESs), energy storage systems (ESSs), and electric vehicles (EVs), inherently operate on dc. Consequently, dc microgrids reduce the need for multiple and costly ac-dc conversions, lower energy losses, enhance overall system efficiency, and provide improved control over power flow [4, 5].

As energy systems continue to evolve, dc microgrids are poised to play a transformative role in future residential applications. With the growing adoption of RESs, such as rooftop solar panels, and the increasing demand for energy-efficient homes and net-zero-energy buildings, dc microgrids offer a pathway to more sustainable and resilient energy management [6, 7]. Residential dc microgrids can directly integrate solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, battery storage, electronic loads, and EV charging, all of which natively operate on dc. By reducing conversion losses, dc microgrids will provide households with cleaner and more reliable energy, while also enabling participation in demand response programs. This decentralized energy management model empowers homeowners to produce, store, and use their own energy, reducing dependence on the centralized grid and contributing to the overall stability and sustainability of urban power networks.

In the commercial and industrial sectors, dc microgrids offer even broader applications. Commercial buildings with high energy demands, such as office complexes, shopping centers, and data centers, can benefit from the efficiency and

FIGURE 1.1: Example of dc microgrids in residential applications.

flexibility provided by dc microgrids. These systems can easily integrate large-scale renewable energy installations, improve energy storage management, and support critical loads during power outages. In industrial settings, dc microgrids are increasingly viewed as a solution for enhancing energy efficiency in manufacturing processes and powering energy-intensive operations [1]. By minimizing energy losses, reducing downtime, and enabling flexible energy sourcing from both renewables and traditional grid power, dc microgrids have the potential to revolutionize how industries manage their energy needs, paving the way for more sustainable and resilient industrial systems.

Given the discussed potentials and motivations for dc microgrids, the future of modern energy systems is increasingly shifting towards hybrid architectures, where conventional ac grids and modern dc microgrids coexist and operate side by side. This hybrid approach is driven by the need to integrate diverse energy sources—such as centralized power plants and decentralized renewable energy systems—into a unified, flexible grid. By coupling ac and dc systems, hybrid energy networks enable the seamless exchange of power between traditional infrastructure and newer, more efficient dc microgrids. This integration allows for optimized energy management, with each system operating under its optimal conditions. AC grids remain well-suited for the existing power infrastructure and conventional loads, while dc microgrids excel at managing local, distributed generation from renewables, energy storage systems, and dc-native loads like electric vehicles and modern electronics.

Power Factor Correction (PFC) converters play a critical role in interfacing ac

FIGURE 1.2: Example of dc microgrids in industrial applications.

and dc systems. First, PFC converters must be capable of handling bidirectional power flow. This functionality is essential for power balancing in dc microgrids, allowing them to export excess power to the ac grid during periods of surplus generation and to import power when needed, ensuring stable and reliable operation. Additionally, PFC converters must maintain high power quality on both the ac and dc sides across the entire operating range. Furthermore, PFC converters need to be optimized for efficiency, power density, cost, and reliability to meet the targeted efficiency and sustainability goals of modern power systems.

1.2 Challenges and Research Gaps of Existing Three-Phase PFC Converters in dc Microgrid applications

This section addresses the challenges and research gaps that directly impact the selection of topologies and the performance of three-phase PFC converters when interfacing with dc microgrids.

1.2.1 Standardization of dc Microgrids Voltage Level

While the voltage level of low-voltage (LV) ac grids is standardized—for instance, the European LV three-phase ac grid operates with a line-to-line RMS voltage $V_{ll,rms}$ of 400 V—the selection of the dc system voltage level remains a significant

FIGURE 1.3: Different nominal voltages and voltage bands of LV dc systems, along with their corresponding shares based on documented use cases.

challenge. Due to the absence of standardized dc voltage levels, various voltage ranges are used in LV dc applications, spanning from 5 V to 1500 V, as shown in Fig. 1.3.

The voltage level of the dc system not only influences the selection of semiconductor devices and passive elements in PFC converters but also directly impacts the choice of topology. Non-isolated three-phase PFC converters can be classified as either buck-type or boost-type, depending on the dc-side voltage level V_{dc} . For connection to the European LV ac grid, buck-type converters are suitable for interfacing with dc systems that have voltages up to 490 V [3]. In contrast, boost-type converters are designed to interface with dc links operating at voltages of 565 V or higher, as shown in Fig. 1.4.

Toward the standardization and optimal selection of the LV dc voltage level, the 400 V dc system shows significant potential for future dc microgrids, particularly in residential and commercial applications. Numerous evaluation studies support the selection of the 400 V dc system by comparing various voltage levels in terms of overall system efficiency, the number of power conversions required to integrate multiple energy sources and loads, as well as safety and protection requirements [8–15]. In addition to these studies, the majority of documented case studies on dc microgrids in residential and commercial applications have also adopted the 400 V dc system [16–23].

FIGURE 1.4: DC voltage range of both three-phase buck and boost PFC converters as a function of the ac grid line-to-line rms voltage.

1.2.2 Grounding of dc Microgrids

The selection of an appropriate grounding configuration for a dc microgrid is directly influenced by the ac grid's grounding scheme. Current state-of-the-art practices, as indicated in previous studies [24–26], typically achieve grounding for both the ac grid and the dc microgrid through isolating both grids either by isolated PFC converters or low-frequency transformers. In the case of non-isolated PFC converters, solid grounding on both the ac and dc sides is not feasible for unipolar dc microgrids [27]. Thus, when the ac grid is grounded, the unipolar dc microgrid typically employs either isolated or high-resistance grounding. However, for bipolar dc microgrids connected to a grounded ac grid via non-isolated converters, grounding both sides is achievable through split-capacitor midpoint grounding [28].

Various studies in the literature have investigated both isolated and non-isolated three-phase PFC converters for interfacing the ac grid with dc microgrids [29]. Non-isolated converters are often preferred for enhancing the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface [30], especially since galvanic isolation is not a mandatory requirement according to relevant standards [31, 32]. This has led to increased research focus on non-isolated PFC converters that provide the capability to ground both the ac and dc sides.

FIGURE 1.5: Representation of a Multiport converter interfacing various sources, loads and storages.

1.2.3 Increased Penetration of Grid-Interfacing Converters in Future Power Systems

The rising popularity of dc systems in residential and commercial settings, as discussed in [33], has prompted a reassessment of conventional grid interfacing approaches. Traditionally, each dc system—such as PV sources, batteries, and dc microgrids—utilized a dedicated converter for connection to the grid [29], a practice that often results in larger system sizes and higher costs. To address these challenges, multiport converters (MPCs) have emerged as promising and efficient solutions [34,35]. MPCs integrate multiple energy ports into a single hub, providing a more streamlined and potentially cost-effective approach. Fig.1.5 illustrates the proposed concept of using a single MPC to interface the utility grid with multiple ac and dc systems.

MPCs offer a multifaceted solution that extends beyond mere cost and size reduction compared to conventional multi-converter approaches. They introduce enhanced flexibility and resilience by enabling direct power exchange between various ports. When used to link dc microgrids with the ac grid, MPCs allow for direct power transfer through the converter, reducing reliance on the utility grid. This strategic integration optimizes power flow among different energy ports and maximizes the utilization and sharing of RESs and ESSs within the dc microgrids, thereby improving overall system performance.

1.3 Main Objectives

The main objectives of this dissertation are:

- To evaluate existing single-stage buck-type PFC converters designed to interface the 400 V dc microgrid with the three-phase ac grid.
- To implement ultra-efficient power converters in order to validate and demonstrate the performance of buck-type PFC converters in dc microgrid applications.
- To propose novel PFC converter topologies aimed at enhancing the performance of dc microgrids.
- To propose novel control techniques for PFC converters to improve the performance of dc microgrids.

1.4 Dissertation Outline

The dissertation is organized in six chapters as follows:

Chapter 2 discusses and evaluates bidirectional single-stage buck-type PFC converters designed to interface the 400 V unipolar dc microgrid with the European LV three-phase ac grid. Three topologies are evaluated: the seven-switch buck converter, the Swiss converter, and the Y-converter. The evaluation is based on semiconductor stresses and losses, magnetic component sizes and losses, and heat sink sizes. The analysis is conducted for a 10 kW converter intended for small commercial or residential applications. The results show that the Y-converter outperforms the other topologies overall, making it a strong candidate for this application.

Chapter 3 introduces a three-phase four-wire bidirectional topology that functions as an interlinking converter for hybrid ac/dc microgrids. The proposed converter offers single-stage power conversion, potentially resulting in high-efficiency operation. It allows for grounding both ac and dc systems without requiring isolation, while delivering improved performance across various operating scenarios, including normal power flow control under balanced conditions, operation during unbalanced conditions, fault-tolerant operation against single-phase faults, and islanded operation.

Chapter 4 introduces the Multiport Y-converter, a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter designed for interfacing the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. The converter enables single-stage power conversion across multiple ports, which can potentially enhance both efficiency and power density. By eliminating bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and transformers, this topology further improves power density and reduces costs. Additionally, the Multiport Y-converter features buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the dc port voltage levels, offering flexibility to interface directly with a wide range of dc systems.

Chapter 5 introduces the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter for interfacing the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. Compared to the Multiport Y-converter, the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter features a simplified structure with fewer semiconductor devices and inductors, while maintaining the same key capabilities, such as single-stage power conversion across multiple ports, buck-boost functionality, and bidirectional power flow at all ports.

Chapter 6 concludes the dissertation by summarizing the key contributions and results achieved throughout the research. Additionally, it discusses potential avenues for future research.

1.5 Main Contributions

The main contributions of this dissertation can be summarized as follows:

- A comparative evaluation of bidirectional single-stage non-isolated buck-type topologies. The topologies evaluated include the Y-converter, the seven-switch converter, and the Swiss converter. The operational principles of these converters are discussed, followed by their evaluation based on multiple criteria: the number of semiconductors, semiconductor stresses and losses, magnetic component sizes and losses, and heat sink size. This evaluation is performed using an analytical power loss model and simulations. Additionally, the design and losses of magnetic elements, as well as the reverse recovery losses of the SiC MOSFETs, are considered. The results indicate that the Y-converter offers superior overall performance compared to the other topologies, making it a promising candidate for this application. A 10 kW prototype of the Y-converter was constructed, demonstrating a peak efficiency of 99.26% and an efficiency of 97.47% at the rated output power.

- Proposing a three-phase four-wire bidirectional topology, named the Four-wire Y-converter, which serves as an interlinking converter for hybrid ac/dc microgrids and features single-stage power conversion. The proposed configuration consists of three four-switch buck-boost modules connected in a star configuration, with the ac microgrid's neutral directly linked to the positive terminal of the dc microgrid. This neutral wire inclusion enables islanded operation of the hybrid microgrid, ensuring a stable power supply for both single-phase and three-phase ac loads. Additionally, the direct connection between the ac microgrid neutral and the dc microgrid's positive terminal enables grounding for both microgrids, a capability previously only achievable with isolated topologies. The Four-wire Y-converter further demonstrates the ability to control positive, negative, and zero sequence components, allowing flexible operation under ac voltage imbalances to mitigate their effects and ensure optimal performance. Furthermore, the converter facilitates independent phase control, enabling fault-tolerant operation, which is demonstrated under single-phase fault conditions. The converter's performance is validated through experimental testing on a 7 kW prototype under various conditions, including balanced and unbalanced AC voltages, single-module disconnection, and islanded operation.
- Proposing a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter, named the Multiport Y-converter, designed to interface the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. When adopted in 400 V dc microgrids applications, the proposed converter enables direct power sharing between DC microgrids, reducing dependence on the ac grid while enhancing both the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface compared to multiple two-port converters. The key motivations for the Multiport Y-converter include its single-stage power conversion across multiple ports, potentially leading to improved efficiency and power density. The absence of bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and transformers further contributes to reduced cost and size. Additionally, the converter features buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the dc ports' voltage levels, offering flexibility to interface directly with a wide range of dc systems. The topology is evaluated for dc port voltages ranging from 350 V to 800 V. To demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed converter, a comprehensive comparison is carried out against two Y-converter topologies and a dc-link coupled multiport converter. The proposed converter's performance is validated through experimental tests under various operating conditions.

- Proposing a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter, named the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, designed to interface the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. The Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter features a more compact structure compared to the Multiport Y-converter, potentially leading to a lower-cost power converter, particularly when interfacing two dc ports with different power levels. Challenges associated with the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, such as maintaining balanced ac grid currents due to its asymmetric structure and minimizing low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports, are addressed with proposed solutions. The performance of the converter is validated through experimental tests under various operating conditions, including steady-state, transient results, and efficiency evaluations.

1.6 List of publications

Journal papers

- J.1 **A. Y. Farag**, T. Younis, D. Biadene and P. Mattavelli, "AC Grid-DC Microgrid Coupling with High-Performance Three-Phase Single-Stage Bidirectional Converters", *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 17, 2023.
- J.2 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli and T. Younis, "Three-Phase Four-Wire Step-Down Modular Converter for an Enhanced Interlinking in Low-Voltage Hybrid AC/DC Microgrids," in *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 5, pp. 634-647, 2024.
- J.3 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Single-Stage Non-Isolated Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking 400 V DC Microgrids with the Three-Phase AC Grid," in *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 5, pp. 1432-1445, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJPEL.2024.3462773.
- J.4 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC systems," **under review** in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*.

Conference papers

- C.1 **A. Y. Farag**, T. Younis, P. Mattavelli and D. Biadene, "AC Grid-interface Bidirectional Buck-Type Converters for DC microgrids: A Comparative

Study," IECON 2022 – 48th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, Brussels, Belgium, 2022, pp. 1-6.

- C.2 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli and T. Younis, "Three-phase Four-wire Bidirectional Y-converter for an Enhanced Interface between the AC Grid and the Unipolar DC Microgrid," 2023 8th IEEE Workshop on the Electronic Grid (eGRID), Karlsruhe, Germany, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- C.3 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC Systems," 2024 IEEE 15th International Symposium on Power Electronics for Distributed Generation Systems (PEDG), Luxembourg, Luxembourg, 2024, pp. 1-6.
- C.4 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Enhancing DC microgrids integration with three-phase AC grids using multiport converters," 13th International Conference on Power Electronics, Machines and Drives (PEMD 2024), Nottingham, UK, 2024, pp. 234-239.
- C.5 **A. Y. Farag**, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC Microgrids," 2024 Energy Conversion Congress & Expo Europe (ECCE Europe), Darmstadt, Germany, 2024, pp. 1-6.

Chapter 2

Comparative Evaluation of Three-phase Single-stage Bidirectional Converters for Interfacing the AC Grid with the DC Microgrid

2.1 Introduction and Background

The rapid increase in the demand for electric energy, particularly in the electric vehicle market, poses significant challenges. Meeting this growing demand requires a corresponding expansion in electric energy generation, which can lead to environmental issues if traditional energy sources are relied upon. Hence, renewable energy sources present an ideal solution for addressing the surging demand while generating zero-carbon emissions. Furthermore, recent advancements in control approaches for renewable energy sources, particularly solar and wind sources, have facilitated the seamless integration of these renewable sources into the preexisting power networks [36–39].

One of the most promising solutions is the utilization of microgrids. Microgrids offer a means to meet local energy demands by connecting distributed power sources to distribution networks, eliminating the need for extensive expansion of costly centralized utility grids. Consequently, DC microgrid technology has emerged as an attractive solution for modern electrical grid systems due to its inherent compatibility with renewable energy sources, electric loads, and energy

FIGURE 2.1: A bidirectional DC/AC converter connecting a DC microgrid to an AC grid.

storage systems [40, 41]. Typically, DC microgrids are interconnected with low- or medium-voltage utility grids, as displayed in Fig. 2.1, to serve as a backup in situations where the load demand exceeds the generated power within the microgrid or to feed surplus-generated power from the microgrid back to the utility grid [24, 42, 43].

Several studies discussed the selection of the DC microgrid optimum voltage level [4, 24, 44, 45]. The findings of these studies have demonstrated that the 400 V DC system yields superior outcomes in terms of system efficiency and necessitates fewer power conversions for connecting multiple energy sources and loads. This voltage level is particularly advantageous for applications such as electric vehicle charging and distribution in residential or commercial buildings. When interconnecting a 400 V DC microgrid with the European low-voltage grid, which operates at a 400 V line-to-line voltage, the use of buck-type bidirectional power factor correction (PFC) converters is necessary [3].

Numerous topologies utilizing optimized modulation techniques have been proposed in the literature to attain an ultra-efficient power conversion in buck-type topologies. The first set of topologies is based on the conventional six-switch buck converter. In an effort to attain 99% efficiency, a design procedure for optimizing the six-switch buck converter is presented in [46]. Different optimized modulation techniques for this topology were explored in [47] to minimize switching losses and input capacitor voltage distortions. A further improvement to the six-switch buck converter is presented in [48, 49], which is called the seven-switch buck converter. In the seven-switch converter, an additional freewheeling switch is employed to reduce conduction losses during the freewheeling mode. Bidirectional power capability for the above-mentioned topologies can be obtained using the anti-parallel configuration or using an inverting link [50, 51]. A delta-type input current source

FIGURE 2.2: Schematic of the isolated Y-converter

converter with bidirectional capability is proposed in [52] to reduce the conduction losses of the six-switch converter.

The second set of topologies is based on employing an active third-harmonic current injection circuit such as the Swiss converter. The Swiss converter was presented in [53] and it demonstrated significant potential for achieving improved performance compared to the conventional six-switch converter. An ultra-high efficiency-interleaved Swiss converter with Silicon Carbide (SiC) devices is demonstrated in [54]. Modified modulation techniques for the Swiss converter are presented in [55, 56] to improve grid current distortions. Moreover, an isolated Swiss converter is reported in [57], which employs full-bridge topology to the Swiss rectifier to attain both the soft switching and the high-frequency galvanic isolation. In addition to the Swiss converter, the hybrid active third-harmonic current injection converter was proposed and compared to the Swiss rectifier in [58], where the Swiss rectifier showed an overall better performance.

In addition to the conventional buck-type converters, the Y-converter, originally introduced in [59] for motor-drive applications, can be utilized to connect the AC grid with the DC microgrid. The Y-converter offers a bidirectional buck–boost capability and enables single-stage power conversion with a reduced number of semiconductor devices compared to traditional buck-type topologies. Consequently, the Y-converter emerges as a compelling choice for interfacing the AC grid with the DC microgrids. Besides the non-isolated topology that is thoroughly discussed in this chapter, an isolated single-stage Y-converter is proposed in [60, 61] utilizing a bidirectional switches as displayed in Fig. 2.2

In this chapter, a comparative evaluation of bidirectional single-stage non-isolated buck-type topologies is conducted. The evaluated converters include the Y-converter, the seven-switch converter, and the Swiss converter. The operational principles of these topologies are discussed, followed by their evaluations based on various criteria: the number of semiconductors, semiconductor stresses and losses, magnetic

element sizes and losses, and the size of the heat sink. This evaluation is carried out using an analytical power loss model and simulations. Additionally, the magnetic element design and losses, along with the reverse recovery losses of the SiC MOSFETs, are included as part of the evaluation criteria. A 10 kW prototype of the Y-converter is implemented to demonstrate its operation and high efficiency. The rest of this chapter is structured as follows: The topology overview is discussed in Section 2.2. Analytical power loss models are presented in Section 2.3. A comparative evaluation of the topologies is presented in Section 2.4. Finally, the experimental results are presented in Section 2.5.

2.2 Topology Overview

In this section, a brief discussion is provided on the three topologies, along with an explanation of their operational principles and the driving pulse schemes employed by each converter.

2.2.1 Y-Converter

Fig. 2.3a illustrates the Y-converter topology. In the standard representation, the Y-converter can be viewed as a conventional three-phase boost voltage source converter with an additional pre-stage to incorporate the buck feature. In the modular representation, the Y-converter is constructed by connecting three four-switch buck–boost DC-DC converters in a star configuration, all connected to a common point (m). For the sake of simplicity, the analysis in this paper will utilize the modular representation.

Since each module functions as a DC-DC converter, it is essential to ensure a positive input voltage at the AC input of the modules ($V_{\{a,b,c\}m}$ must be kept ≥ 0 V). To achieve this, a suitable offset voltage must be established between the grid neutrals (n) and (m). Different pulse-width modulation (PWM) techniques can be employed based on the selected offset voltage [59, 62]. The PWM technique considered in this paper is the discontinuous PWM (DPWM), which provides a time-varying offset voltage represented by:

$$v_{off}(t) = -\min(v_a(t), v_b(t), v_c(t)) \quad (2.1)$$

where v_a , v_b , and v_c are the AC grid phase voltages.

FIGURE 2.3: The three buck-type converters. (a) Y-converter; (b) seven-switch converter; and (c) Swiss converter.

The AC-side voltages (v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm}) of the three modules can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} v_{am} &= \hat{V}_m \cos(\omega t) + v_{off} \\ v_{bm} &= \hat{V}_m \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + v_{off} \\ v_{cm} &= \hat{V}_m \cos\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + v_{off} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

where \hat{V}_m is the peak value of the phase voltages.

In DPWM, the module with the most-negative grid voltage is clamped to point m . This clamping mode has the advantage of eliminating both semiconductor switching losses and inductor core losses for the clamped module, resulting in a significant reduction in overall losses. During the remaining part of the fundamental cycle, one half-bridge (either the buck or boost) is subjected to pulse width modulation, while the other half-bridge is clamped. The choice of modulation depends on whether the AC-side module voltage is higher or lower than the DC-side voltage. The Y-converter modulation and the duty cycles of the switches are depicted in Fig. 2.4a.

2.2.2 Seven-Switch Buck Converter

The seven-switch buck converter comprises three main parts: a three-phase bridge, a freewheeling switch, and an inverting link. In this analysis, the three-phase bridge is created using a series combination of SiC MOSFETs and SiC diodes that enable current flow in one direction and voltage blocking in both directions.

The converter operation is analyzed using space vector PWM (SVPWM) [49] and involves six active space vectors and a zero (null) space vector. The zero-space vector is achieved by activating only the freewheeling switch, whereas in the traditional six-switch topology, the entire leg is turned on. During the freewheeling state, the seven-switch converter has the advantage of the DC link current flowing through a single semiconductor device S_{fw} , resulting in significantly reduced conduction losses compared to the four devices in the six-switch converter.

To enable bidirectional power capability, the inverting link is utilized to reverse the polarity of the DC-side voltage. In the rectification mode, the inverting link switches, such as S_{i+} and S_{i-} , are turned off, allowing power transfer from the AC side to the DC side through D_{i+} and D_{i-} . In the inversion mode, both S_{i+} and

S_{i-} are turned on, creating a negative DC link that facilitates power transfer from the DC side to the AC side. The seven-switch buck converter modulation and the duty cycles of the switches are presented in Fig. 2.4b.

2.2.3 Swiss Converter

The Swiss converter is composed of three primary stages: an active three-phase bridge, a third harmonic injection network, and two buck DC-DC converters. The three-phase bridge operates as a synchronous rectification stage, as an uncontrolled/diode rectifier bridge.

The third harmonic injection network includes three four-quadrant switches and is controlled to actively inject current solely into the phase with the lowest instantaneous voltage. Switching losses in both the active bridge and the injection network are neglected since they operate at the grid frequency and twice the grid frequency, respectively. When combined, the active bridge and the injection network form a three-phase unfold. This three-phase AC unfold converts the three-phase voltages into two DC voltages, namely v_{py} and v_{yn} , which are utilized by the two buck DC-DC converters. This configuration enables the control of grid currents and the DC-side voltage by solely manipulating the duty cycle of the buck converters.

The duty cycles d_{p+} of switch S_{p+} and d_{n-} of switch S_{n-} are controlled in both the inverter and rectifier modes so that the AC-side current becomes sinusoidal. d_{p+} and d_{n-} can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{p+} &= \frac{2V_{dc}}{3\hat{V}_m^2} \max(v_a, v_b, v_c) \\ d_{n-} &= \frac{2V_{dc}}{3\hat{V}_m^2} |\min(v_a, v_b, v_c)| \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

where V_{dc} is the DC link voltage. The Swiss converter modulation and the duty cycles of the switches are presented in Fig. 2.4c.

2.3 Analytical Power Loss Model

To assess and compare the three topologies, an analytical model is developed to calculate power losses. The model takes into account various types of power losses: including conduction losses and switching losses in the semiconductors, copper and

FIGURE 2.4: Modulation techniques for the three topologies. (a) Y-converter; (b) seven-switch converter; and (c) Swiss converter.

	Parameter	Symbol	Value
Converter parameters	Nominal power	P	10 kW
	AC line rms voltage	V_{ac}	400 V
	Line frequency	f	50 Hz
	Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
	Output voltage	V_{dc}	400 V
SiC MOSFET	Part number	IMZ120R030M1H	
	Voltage	V_{DS}	1200 V
	Current	I_D	56 A
SiC Diode	Part number	C4D20120D	
	Voltage	V_{RRM}	1200 V
	Current	I_F	66 A
Input Filter	Inductor	L_f	50 μ H
	Capacitor	C_f	11.3 μ F

TABLE 2.1: Three-phase PFC rectifier parameters utilized in both the evaluation of the converters and the experimental prototype.

core losses in the inductors. Table 2.1 summarizes the converter parameters and the used semiconductors. The model is based on the following assumptions:

1. The inductances in all converters are assumed to be constant for the whole operating power range;
2. The comparison is held at a fixed junction temperature for all devices;
3. The reverse recovery losses of the SiC Schottky diode are neglected as a zero-reverse recovery current diode is utilized.
4. The input filter (L_f, C_f) is fixed for all topologies; the EMI filter is not considered.

2.3.1 Semiconductor Conduction Losses

The conduction losses of the power MOSFETs are calculated as follows:

$$P_{cond,sw} = I_{DS,RMS}^2 R_{DS,on} \quad (2.4)$$

where $I_{DS,RMS}$ is the RMS value of the MOSFET current, and these RMS values for the three topologies are summarized in Fig. 2.5. $R_{DS,on}$ is the on-state resistance of the power MOSFET and it is assumed to vary with the junction temperature T_j according to the following equation:

$$R_{DS,on}(m\Omega) = a_0 + a_1 T_j + a_2 T_j^2 \quad (2.5)$$

The used fitting parameters for IMZ120R030M1H are:

$$a_0 = 29.78 \text{ m}\Omega, \quad a_1 = -0.01556 \text{ m}\Omega/^\circ\text{C}, \quad a_2 = 0.0009778 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}\Omega/^\circ\text{C}^2 \quad (2.6)$$

For the SiC diodes in the seven-switch converter, the conduction losses are calculated as follows:

$$P_{cond,D} = I_{D,rms}^2 R_{D,on} + I_{D,av} V_{D,on} \quad (2.7)$$

where $I_{D,rms}$ and $I_{D,av}$ are the RMS and the average values of the diode current, respectively. These values are summarized in Fig. 2.5. $R_{D,on}$ and $V_{D,on}$ are the on-state resistance and the on-state voltage of the power diode and they are assumed to vary with the junction temperature T_j , according to the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{D \text{ on}}(m\Omega) &= b_0 + b_1 T_j \\ V_{D \text{ on}}(V) &= c_0 + c_1 T_j \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

The used fitting parameters for C4D20120D are:

$$b_0 = 20 \text{ m}\Omega, \quad b_1 = 0.266 \text{ m}\Omega/^\circ\text{C}, \quad c_0 = 0.98 \text{ V}, \quad c_1 = -1.71 \times 10^{-3} \text{ V}/^\circ\text{C} \quad (2.9)$$

2.3.2 Semiconductors Switching Losses

The calculation of switching losses relies on the utilization of switching energy loss E_{sw} versus drain-source current I_{DS} curves of the SiC MOSFETs. These curves can be obtained from the manufacturer's datasheet or through the implementation of a

	Y-Converter			Seven-switch Converter			Swiss Converter								
Inductor	RMS	$I_{L,\text{RMS}} = \frac{I_{dc}}{4\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{12M^2 - \frac{16}{\sqrt{3}}M + 16}$			RMS	$I_{L,\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{I_{dc}^2 + \frac{\Delta I_L^2}{18}}$			RMS	$I_{L,\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{I_{dc}^2 + \frac{\Delta I_L^2}{18}}$					
Semiconductors current	$S_{\{a,b,c\}1}$	RMS	$\frac{I_{L,\text{RMS}}}{M}\sqrt{-\frac{M^2}{6} + \frac{20}{21}M - \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{9\pi}}$			$S_{1:6}$	RMS	$I_{dc}\sqrt{\frac{M}{\pi}}$			$S_{p\{a,b,c\}}$	RMS	$I_{dc}\sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{3}M}{2\pi}}$		
	$S_{\{a,b,c\}2}$		$\frac{I_{L,\text{RMS}}}{M}\sqrt{\frac{7M^2}{6} - \frac{20}{21}M + \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{9\pi}}$			S_{fw}		$I_{dc}\sqrt{1 - \frac{3M}{\pi}}$			$S_{\{a,b,c\}n}$		$I_{dc}\sqrt{\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{2\pi}}$		
	$S_{\{a,b,c\}3}$		$\frac{I_{L,\text{RMS}}}{M}\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{2}{\pi}\right)M^2 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}M + \frac{4}{9\pi}}$			$S_{i+,i-}$		$\sqrt{3}I_{dc}\sqrt{\frac{M}{\pi}}$			$S_{y+,y-}$		$I_{dc}\sqrt{1 - \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{2\pi}}$		
	$S_{\{a,b,c\}4}$		$\frac{I_{L,\text{RMS}}}{M}\sqrt{-\frac{2}{\pi}M^2 + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}M - \frac{4}{9\pi}}$			$D_{1:6}$ $D_{i+,i-}$		$I_{dc}M/\pi$ $3I_{dc}M/\pi$			$S_{\{a,b,c\}y}$		$I_{dc}\sqrt{(2 - \sqrt{3})M}$		

FIGURE 2.5: The stresses of the different semiconductor devices in the three topologies.

calorimetric switching loss measurement setup, as suggested in [63]. In this paper, two distinct polynomial fittings are employed to determine the turn-on energy loss $E_{sw,on}$ and the turn-off energy loss $E_{sw,off}$ individually. This separation allows for easy integration of soft switching into the power loss model whenever it occurs. The polynomial fitting equations for $E_{sw,on}$ and $E_{sw,off}$ are chosen to be fourth-order polynomials in order to minimize the root mean square error between the actual data and the fitted polynomials. The polynomial fitting equations can be expressed as:

$$E_{sw,on} \text{ (mJ)} = V_{DS} (P_{1\text{ on}} I_{DS\text{ on}}^4 + P_{2\text{ on}} I_{DS\text{ on}}^3 + P_{3\text{ on}} I_{DS\text{ on}}^2 + P_{4\text{ on}} I_{DS\text{ on}}) \quad (2.10)$$

$$E_{sw,off} \text{ (mJ)} = V_{DS} (P_{1\text{ off}} I_{DS\text{ off}}^4 + P_{2\text{ off}} I_{DS\text{ off}}^3 + P_{3\text{ off}} I_{DS\text{ off}}^2 + P_{4\text{ off}} I_{DS\text{ off}}) \quad (2.11)$$

where $I_{DS,on}$ and $I_{DS,off}$ are the current values of the mosfet at the turn-on and turn-off instants, respectively, and V_{DS} is the drain-source voltage at the off state. The fitting parameters for IMZ120R030M1H are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{1\text{ on}} &= -7.2730 \times 10^{-10} \text{ A}^{-3}\text{ms}; & P_{1\text{ off}} &= -5.4688 \times 10^{-10} \text{ A}^{-3}\text{ms} \\ P_{2\text{ on}} &= +7.0371 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A}^{-2}\text{ms}; & P_{2\text{ off}} &= +5.2350 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A}^{-2}\text{ms} \\ P_{3\text{ on}} &= -2.1250 \times 10^{-6} \text{ A}^{-1}\text{ms}; & P_{3\text{ off}} &= -1.4412 \times 10^{-6} \text{ A}^{-1}\text{ms} \\ P_{4\text{ on}} &= +3.6750 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ms}; & P_{4\text{ off}} &= +1.5450 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ms} \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Given the switch voltage and current at the turn-on and turn-off instances, the switching energy is calculated using (2.10) and (2.11), then the switching losses

are calculated.

In addition to the switching losses during the first quadrant operation of SiC MOSFETs, the power loss model includes switching losses during the third quadrant operation, (i.e., the synchronous rectification mode). We assume that the turn-on switching losses in the synchronous rectifier mode are negligible, while at turn-off, power loss occurs due to the reverse recovery of the integral body diode. The switching energy losses due to reverse recovery ($E_{sw_{rr}}$) can be represented as functions of I_{ds} and V_{sw} [64] based on the following polynomial fitting:

The fitting parameters for IMZ120R030M1H are as follows:

$$E_{sw_{rr}}(\text{mJ}) = V_{DS} (P_{1_{rr}} I_{sw_{off}}^2 + P_{2_{rr}} I_{sw_{off}} + P_{3_{rr}}) \quad (2.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{1_{rr}} &= +1.4037 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A}^{-1}\text{ms} \\ P_{2_{rr}} &= +1.1225 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ms} \\ P_{3_{rr}} &= +2.8075 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Ams} \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

2.3.3 Inductor Losses:

The power inductor L is designed to provide the same inductor current ripple percentage at the rated power for all topologies ($\Delta I_{Lp} = 20\%$). It can be calculated for the Y-converter as follows [62]:

$$L = \frac{V_{dc}}{8\sqrt{2}\Delta I_{Lp}I_{\varphi}f_{sw}} \quad (2.15)$$

For the Swiss and seven-switch converters [46, 53]:

$$L = \frac{V_{dc}}{2\Delta I_{Lp}I_{dc}f_{sw}} \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2M}\right) \quad (2.16)$$

where M is the modulation index and can be expressed as follows:

$$M = \sqrt{2} \frac{I_{\varphi}}{I_{dc}} = \frac{2V_{dc}}{3V_m} \quad (2.17)$$

where I_{dc} is the DC-side current and I_{φ} is the RMS value of the AC-side phase current.

At the given M (≈ 0.8165), previous equations result in almost the same value of L ($\approx 190 \mu H$) for the investigated topologies.

The power loss of L is divided into copper losses and core losses. For the copper losses, due to employing Litz wires, skin effects and high-frequency losses can be neglected. Therefore, the copper losses are limited to the DC copper losses, which can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{cu} = I_{Lrms}^2 R_{LDC} \quad (2.18)$$

where R_{LDC} is the DC resistance of L .

The core loss is calculated based on the curve-fitting equations provided by the manufacturer [65]. The provided fitting equations represent experimentally measured magnetic property curves using closed-form equations. These equations facilitate the seamless integration of these magnetic properties into the power loss model. Starting from the maximum and minimum currents of the inductor at different instances, $I_{Lmax,i}$, $I_{Lmin,i}$, the corresponding values of magnetic flux intensity (H) and magnetic flux density (B) can be calculated as follows:

$$H = \frac{0.4\pi N I_L}{100 \text{ MPL}} \quad (2.19)$$

$$B = \left[\frac{a + bH + cH^2}{1 + dH + eH^2} \right]^x \quad (2.20)$$

where N is the number of turns, MPL is the average magnetic path length in meters (m), H is in Oersted (Oe), and B is in Tesla (T). The a , b , c , d , e , and x terms are the fitting parameters of the B-H curves provided by the manufacturer. The values of these fitting parameters are summarized in Table 2.2.

The core losses at a specific instant can be given by:

$$P_{core} = V_c \times a_{Loss} \times (B_{max} - B_{min})^{b_{Loss}} \left(\frac{f_{sw}}{1000} \right)^{c_{Loss}} \quad (2.21)$$

where V_c is the magnetic core volume in m^3 , and the terms a_{Loss} , b_{Loss} , and c_{Loss} are the fitting parameters for the core loss curves provided by the manufacturer. The inductor parameters along with the core loss fitting parameters are summarized in Table 2.2.

	Parameter	Symbol	Value	
Inductor Parameters	Part number		KoolMu 0079908A7	
	Magnetic path length	MPL	19.6 cm	
	Core volume	V_c	43.4 cm ³	
	Number of turns	N	80 Turns	
	Inductor DC resistance	R_{LDC}	20.3 m Ω	
Fitting Parameters	Flux density B Equation (2.20)	a	3.763×10^{-2} T	
		b	1.712×10^{-2} T/Oe	
		c	5.155×10^{-4} T/Oe ²	
		d	9.190×10^{-2} Oe ⁻¹	
		e	4.909×10^{-4} Oe ⁻²	
		x	1.812	
		Core losses P_{core} Equation (2.21)	a_{Loss}	52.36 J/(T.m ³)
			b_{Loss}	1.988
			c_{Loss}	1.541

TABLE 2.2: Inductor parameters.

2.4 Comparative Evaluation

2.4.1 Semiconductors Stresses

2.4.1.1 Voltage Stresses

In the three topologies, the maximum voltage stress on semiconductor devices is represented by three distinct values: the peak line-to-line grid voltage (566 V), the DC microgrid voltage (400 V), and the natural commutation points of the output voltage of uncontrolled bridge rectifier (490 V). The 566 V peak voltage applies to the AC-side SiC MOSFETs ($S_{\{a,b,c\}1}$ and $S_{\{a,b,c\}2}$) in the Y-converter, the three-phase bridge devices ($S_{1:6}$ and $D_{1:6}$) in the seven-switch converter, and the three-phase bridge devices ($S_{1:6}$) in the Swiss converter. The 400 V peak voltage is applicable to the remaining devices in the Y-converter and the seven-switch converter, while the 490 V peak voltage applies to the remaining devices in

FIGURE 2.6: Summation of the squared RMS currents of semiconductor devices of the studied topologies.

the Swiss converter. The voltage stresses of the three topologies are summarized in Fig. 2.7.

2.4.1.2 Current Stresses

The formulas for the current stresses of the semiconductor devices in the three topologies are summarized in Fig. 2.5. Additionally, the current stresses at 10 kW are summarized in Fig. 2.7.

In order to provide deeper insight into the current stresses of the investigated topologies, the summation of the squared RMS currents of semiconductor devices as a function of the output power in the investigated topologies are depicted in Fig. 2.6. According to the obtained outcomes, the Y-converter exhibits the lowest summation across the entire power range. This implies that the Y-converter necessitates semiconductor devices with a lower current rating in comparison to the seven-switch and Swiss converters. Furthermore, if the same SiC devices are employed for all three topologies, the Y-converter will incur the least conduction losses at any given power level.

2.4.2 Semiconductors Losses

2.4.2.1 Conduction Losses

The estimated conduction losses of the semiconductor devices are reported in Fig. 2.8a for the considered topologies. The Y-converter exhibits the lowest conduction losses throughout the entire operating range. This is primarily due to its minimal number of series switches in the current path for rectification and inversion. On the other hand, the seven-switch converter experiences the highest conduction losses. This can be attributed to the presence of SiC diodes and the excessive current stresses on the inverting link devices.

FIGURE 2.7: Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the number of semiconductors, semiconductor stresses and losses, the size of the heat sink, and the magnetic element sizes.

2.4.2.2 Switching Losses

The switching losses of the three topologies are estimated and collected in Fig. 2.8b. In the Y-converter, the use of DPWM leads to a significant reduction in switching losses. Additionally, only a single leg in each module undergoes commutation at any given time, further contributing to lower losses. In the Swiss converter, although the switching losses are confined to the fast switches (S_{p+} and S_{n-} in the rectification mode and S_{y+} and S_{y-} in the inversion mode), they are considerably high due to their operation under high currents. Given the semiconductor conduction and switching losses of the studied topologies, the total semiconductor losses are plotted in Fig. 2.8c.

2.4.3 Inductor Losses

The inductor losses of the topologies are plotted in Fig. 2.9. Although the core losses in the Y-converter are reduced by employing DPWM, the Y-converter demonstrates the highest core losses among the studied topologies. The inductors in the Swiss converter and the seven-switch converters yield the same losses and sizes. The copper losses in the Y-converter are reduced as the total current is shared between the three phases, unlike the other topologies, where the total output current flows through the inductors.

2.5 Experimental Results

To demonstrate the operation and high efficiency of the Y-converter, a 10-kW prototype of the Y-converter is implemented. The experimental setup is displayed in Fig. 2.10. The experimental results are categorized as follows: key waveforms of the Y-converter, along with the measured total harmonic distortion (THD) of the AC side currents, and the measured efficiency of the converter, with its corresponding calculated power loss breakdown.

2.5.1 Key Waveforms and AC Current THDs

The selected key waveforms of the Y-converter are the AC-side voltage V_{am} , the grid voltage V_{an} , the inductor current I_{La} , and the grid current I_a . Experimental results under full loads for both rectification and inversion modes are displayed in Fig. 2.11 and Fig. 2.12, respectively. The results show that the clamping mode is

FIGURE 2.8: Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the semiconductor losses across the entire power operation range. Subfigures (a), (b), and (c) depict different loss components: conduction losses, switching losses, and semiconductor losses, respectively.

verified where $V_{am} = 0$ V, and I_{La} is shown to be ripple-free during clamping while preserving the sinusoidal shapes of both I_{La} and I_a . The THDs of I_a at different output power levels are presented in Fig. 2.13 with 3.8% at the converter's rated output power.

2.5.2 Measured Efficiency and Power Loss Breakdown

The efficiency of the prototype is measured using the Dewesoft SIRIUS XHS high-speed data acquisition (DAQ) system. The efficiency curve is plotted in Fig. 2.13, which shows that the converter has a peak efficiency of 99.26% at nearly 40% of the rated power and 97.49% efficiency at the rated power.

Based on the previously discussed power loss model and the measured temperatures of the semiconductor devices during experimental tests, the calculated power

FIGURE 2.9: Comparison between the three topologies in terms of the inductor losses across the entire power operation range.

FIGURE 2.10: Picture of the Y-converter prototype.

loss breakdown for a half load and full load are displayed in Fig. 2.14. At a half load, the semiconductor losses represent almost 60% of the total losses with a roughly equalized distribution between conduction losses and switching losses. At a full load, the conduction loss contribution to the total losses is estimated to be 51%, which explicitly means that using different SiC devices with a lower $R_{DS,on}$ can lead to better efficiency at a full load. The “other losses” term, represented in the loss breakdown figure, comprises the losses that are not included in the calculations, such as PCB losses, capacitor losses, etc., along with the mismatch between the calculated losses and the actual losses.

FIGURE 2.11: Key waveforms of the rectification mode at rated power.

FIGURE 2.12: Key waveforms of the inversion mode at rated power.

FIGURE 2.13: Measured efficiency of the prototype.

FIGURE 2.14: Loss Breakdown.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter evaluates bidirectional step-down converters that enable the connection between the 400 V unipolar dc microgrid and the European low-voltage three-phase ac grid. The study compares three single-stage non-isolated topologies—the seven-switch buck converter, Swiss converter, and Y-converter—based on various factors, such as semiconductor stresses and losses, magnetic component sizes and losses, and heat sink sizes. The analysis is centered on a 10 kW converter that is suitable for residential or commercial use. The results indicate that the Y-converter has the lowest number of semiconductor devices, semiconductor device stresses, total losses, and heat sink sizes. The only drawback is that the total inductor size in the Y-converter is larger than those of the other studied topologies. Based on the findings, the Y-converter performs better overall than the other topologies, making it a potentially more suitable option for this application. A 10 kW Y-converter prototype is implemented and shown to have a peak efficiency of 99.26% and an efficiency of 97.47% at the rated output power.

Chapter 3

Four-wire Y-converter for an Enhanced Interlinking in Hybrid Microgrids

3.1 Introduction and Background

The growing utilization of renewable energy sources (RES), energy storage systems (ESS), and electric vehicle charging stations is fueling the requirement for traditional power systems to adapt and handle larger capacities and loads. To effectively integrate distributed energy generation and meet local demand, one possible solution is the adoption of microgrids (MGs) instead of solely relying on conventional utility grids with centralized generation [5, 66, 67]. While AC MGs have the advantage of compatibility with existing utility grids and consumer loads, DC MGs have emerged as strong candidates due to their natural interface with photovoltaic and energy storage systems, along with the increased penetration of DC loads such as electronic loads and electric vehicles [4, 68]. Therefore, hybrid AC/DC MGs can offer an optimized solution by combining the merits of both AC and DC MGs [69–71]. A power-bidirectional interface converter, interlinking the AC and DC links of the hybrid MGs, as presented in Fig. 3.1, is typically used for power exchange and to ensure the stable operation of the hybrid MGs.

A key criterion in the selection and design of the converter topology for hybrid MG interlinking converters (ILCs) is specifying the voltage levels of both the AC and DC links, which poses a challenge in MG applications. While the AC link voltage level is standardized (for example, the European low-voltage (LV) grid operates with a line-to-line voltage of $400 V_{\text{RMS}}$), the selection of the DC link

FIGURE 3.1: A bidirectional converter connecting a DC MG to an AC MG in hybrid MG

voltage level is a significant challenge. Several voltage levels are presented in LV DC applications, ranging from 12 V up to 1500 V. Toward the standardization and optimal selection of the LV DC voltage level, studies conducted in [72, 73] compared different voltage levels in terms of overall system efficiency, the number of power conversions required to connect multiple energy sources and loads, and safety and protection requirements. As a result, the 400 V DC system has been proven to result in superior performance compared to other voltage levels, specifically for residential and commercial applications.

The hybrid MG ILCs can be classified either by their the DC voltage level, as buck-type or boost-type converters, or by the use of the AC neutral wire, resulting in three-wire (3-W) or four-wire (4-W) converters. When connected to the LV European AC grid, buck-type converters are capable of interfacing DC systems with 490 V or lower, therefore can directly interface the 400 V DC link. In contrast, the boost-type converters are capable of interfacing DC links with 565 V or higher [3].

Optimized buck-type converters have been proposed in the literature, including the six-switch current source converter (CSC) [46], the seven-switch CSC [49], the delta-type input CSC [52], and the Swiss converter [54]. The modular buck-boost Y-connected converter, as described in [74], serves as a buck-type bidirectional PFC converter and demonstrates superior overall performance compared to the seven-switch and Swiss converters. As for boost-type converters, the conventional

choice for ILCs is the two-level voltage source converter (2L VSC), acknowledged for its simple structure, control, and high power density [75, 76]. An improved overall performance can be attained with the three-level voltage source converters (3L VSC) compared to the conventional 2L VSC [77]. However, when interfacing the 400 V DC systems, an additional buck stage is needed which can be realized using the DC-DC buck converter [78, 79] or by isolated DC-DC converters [80]. The addition of an extra power conversion stage and the need for an intermediate DC link capacitors degrades the overall efficiency and power density of the ILC.

Considering 3-W and 4-W converters, the extension of the 3-W boost-type converters into 4-W converters have been extensively addressed in the literature either by adding an extra leg to the conventional 2L and 3L VSCs or by connecting the neutral wire to the mid-point of the split DC link [81–86]. However 4-W buck-type converters are rarely discussed in the literature, except for some studies focusing on the suppression of common-mode voltage (CMV) and leakage current in the six-switch CSC [87, 88]. A summary of various ILC topologies is presented in Table 3.1, where the different topologies are subcategorized based on common features. The subcategories are then highlighted based on specific aspects of each solution, such as the voltage level of the DC side, the provision of isolation, the possibility of grounding both AC and DC sides, or the allowance for partial grounding of only the AC side. Additionally, the key motivations and challenges for each topology are provided. This summary emphasizes the existing research gap in proposing a 4-W buck-type converter that facilitates a direct interlinking between the AC and DC MGs without the need for an additional power conversion stage.

Topology	No. of wires	DC-link voltage	Isolation	Grounding	Motivations	Challenges
2L VSC [75]	3	800	NO	Partial	- Simple structure and control	- Need an additional buck stage
Four-leg VSC [81]	4	800	NO	Partial	- Continuous current at AC side	- Intermediate DC link capacitors size
					- Reduced current stresses	- Increased voltage stresses
T-type VSC [77]	3	650	NO	Partial	- Reduced voltage stresses compared to 2L VSC	- Need an additional buck stage
Neutral-point clamped (NPC) VSC [77]	3	650	NO	Partial	- Continuous current at AC side	- Intermediate DC link capacitors size
Four-leg T-type VSC [83]	4	800	NO	Partial	- Reduced current stresses	- Complex structure and control compared to 2L VSC
Four-leg NPC VSC [86]	4	750	NO	Partial		
Six-switch CSC [46]	3	400	NO	Partial		
Seven-switch CSC [49]	3	400	NO	Partial	- Single-stage power conversion	- Discontinuous current at AC side
Delta-type input CSC [52]	3	400	NO	Partial	- Reduced voltage stresses	- Inductor and input filter size
Swiss converter [54]	3	400	NO	Partial	- Inherent short-circuit protection	- Complex structure and control compared to 2L VSC
Y-converter [74]	3	400	NO	Partial		
VSC + DC-DC buck [78, 79]	3	400	NO	Partial	- Simple structure and control	- Reduced efficiency and power density
					- Continuous current at AC side	- Intermediate DC link capacitors size
						- Increased voltage stresses
VSC + DC transformer [80]	3	400	YES	YES	- Isolation between AC and DC MGs	- Reduced efficiency and power density
					- Grounding both AC and DC MGs	- DC transformer size and cost
					- Continuous current at AC side	- Intermediate DC link capacitors size
Power transformer + VSC [89]	3	700	YES	YES	- Isolation between AC and DC MGs	- Reduced efficiency and power density
					- Grounding both AC and DC MGs	- Power transformer size and cost
					- Continuous current at AC side	- Need an additional buck stage in case of 1:1 transformer
Proposed herein	4	400	NO	YES	- Single-stage power conversion	- Discontinuous current at AC side
					- Four-wire buck-type converter	- Inductor and input filter size
					- Grounding both AC and DC MGs without isolation	
					- Reduced voltage stresses	

TABLE 3.1: Summary of the different topologies proposed in the literature for interlinking converters (ILCs), highlighting the key differences between the topologies, as well as the key motivations and challenges of each

Several motivations drive the adoption of 4-W converters in ILC hybrid MGs. Firstly, 4-W converters can support the islanded operation of the hybrid MG, providing a stable power supply for both single-phase and three-phase AC loads [90, 91]. 3-W converters are unable to supply single-phase loads in islanded operation due to the absence of the neutral wire. Therefore, 4-W converters have gained prominence, especially due to the priority of islanded operation in hybrid MG control and the prevalence of single-phase loads in residential LV AC systems [29]. In addition, in the event of voltage imbalance in the AC MG, 3-W converters can only regulate the positive and negative sequence components of the current. This leads to a circulating current, resulting in additional power losses in the hybrid MG [84]. In contrast, 4-W converters are capable of controlling positive, negative, and zero sequence components, allowing for more flexible control to mitigate the effects of voltage imbalances and ensure optimal operation. Furthermore, 4-W converters enable independent control of the three phases, enabling fault-tolerant operation [92]. In case of a single-phase fault in the AC MG, the remaining two phases can still deliver up to two-thirds of the rated output power.

Another critical asset offered by the proposed converter is its ability to ground both the AC MG and the DC MG. While grounding the bipolar DC MG, linked to a grounded AC MG through a non-isolated converter, is achievable using split-capacitor mid-point grounding [28], grounding the unipolar DC MG presents challenges. As indicated in previous studies [24–26], grounding both the AC MG and the DC MG is typically accomplished only through isolated converters or low-frequency transformers. In the proposed topology, grounding both sides is achieved through the direct connection between the neutral of the AC MG (n) and the positive rail of the DC MG.

The adopted approach of grounding the positive rail aligns with the requirements of the European Low Voltage Directive, LVD 2006/95/EC [93], which stipulates that the DC MG should be grounded on either the positive or negative DC rail, and the proposed topology facilitates positive rail grounding. Additionally, for DC MG, positive rail grounding is preferable compared to negative rail grounding to minimize the impact of corrosion [94]. According to [95, 96], grounding the DC MG offers numerous advantages, such as low CMV, low transient over-voltages, no grounding loss, and increased personnel safety.

This chapter proposes a three-phase four-wire buck-type converter, as illustrated in Fig. 3.2, with the aim of enhancing the interlinking between the AC MG and the DC MG. This enhanced interlinking is achieved through a highly efficient converter, enabled by single-stage power conversion. Additionally, optimized performance of the ILC is ensured across various operating scenarios. These scenarios

FIGURE 3.2: A schematic of the proposed four-wire modular converter

encompass normal power flow control under balanced conditions, operation during unbalanced conditions, fault-tolerant operation against single-phase faults, and islanded operation. Compared to state-of-the-art ILCs summarized in Table 3.1, the key advantages of the proposed converter include:

- The proposed converter has the capability to ground both the AC microgrid and the unipolar DC microgrid without the need for isolation.
- In comparison to CSCs, the proposed converter features a 4-W configuration. This configuration enables flexible control in unbalanced conditions, improves fault tolerance, and allows for islanded operation to support both single-phase and three-phase loads.
- In contrast to VSCs, the proposed converter incorporates a single-stage power conversion. This feature potentially contributes to improved efficiency and power density. While VSCs require an additional buck stage to interface with the 400 V DC MG.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows: Section 3.2 explains the converter operation and analysis, Section 3.3 includes an evaluation of the proposed converter, Section 3.4 presents the converter's control structure and modulation, Section 3.5 includes the simulation results and finally, Section 3.6 showcases the experimental results.

3.2 Analysis of the Proposed Converter

The proposed converter extends the 3-W topology, introduced in [97] for motor drive applications, into a 4-W configuration. This section provides a discussion of

both the 3-W and 4-W topologies, emphasizing the operational principles of each and highlighting the key similarities and distinctions between them.

The conventional 3-W topology is constructed by connecting three buck-boost modules at a central point known as (m), which serves as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. Since each module operates as a DC-DC converter, it is essential to maintain a non-negative voltage on the AC side of the module ($V_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0$ V). To accomplish this, an offset voltage is required between (n) and (m). In sinusoidal pulse width modulation (SPWM), a constant offset voltage, denoted as V_{off} , is applied and it is controlled to be greater than the peak value of the grid's AC phase voltage (\hat{V}_m). The AC-side voltages v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be expressed as:

$$v_{xm} = v_x + V_{off} \quad (3.1)$$

where v_x , with $x = (a, b, c)$, are the phase grid voltages and ω is the AC grid frequency in rad/s.

In the case of the 4-W topology presented in Fig. 3.2, the neutral wire (n) is connected to the positive rail of the DC side, which leads to a fixed offset voltage equivalent to the DC-side voltage V_{dc} . To ensure the correct functioning of the four-wire converter when connected to the European distribution grid, V_{dc} needs to exceed 325 V. Therefore, this topology can be utilized to interface the 400 V DC microgrid with the European low-voltage grid. For the 4-W topology, v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{am} &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc} \\ v_{bm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + V_{dc} \\ v_{cm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + V_{dc} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

To provide a clear and simplified analysis, a single-module analysis is provided, which can be extended similarly to the other modules. Considering phase a , displayed in Fig. 3.3a, its module consists of an inductor L and two half-bridges: an AC-side half bridge (S_{a1} , S_{a2}) and a DC-side half bridge (S_{a3} , S_{a4}). These two half-bridges are controlled so that only one half-bridge is modulated at an instance and the other is kept clamped depending on the values of V_{am} and V_{dc} .

When v_{am} is greater than V_{dc} , module a works in the buck mode where the AC-side half bridge is switching, while the DC-side half bridge is clamped (S_{a3} is

FIGURE 3.3: Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter include current paths in both buck and boost modes

kept ON and S_{a4} is kept OFF) as presented in Fig. 3.3b. In this mode, the duty cycle of S_{a1} , which is named $d_{buck,a}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{buck,a} = \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{am}} = \frac{V_{dc}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}} \quad (3.3)$$

and the command of S_{a2} is the complementary of S_{a1} .

Assuming sinusoidal mains current with unity power factor, the average inductor current of module *a*, denoted as $i_{L_{a,av}}$, can be determined as follows:

$$i_{L_{a,av}} = \frac{i_a - i_{C_{f,a}}}{d_{buck,a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) - i_{C_{f,a}}}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (3.4)$$

where i_a is the grid current of phase *a*, $i_{C_{f,a}}$ is the current of the input capacitor C_f , and \hat{I}_m is the peak grid current. By neglecting $i_{C_{f,a}}$ compared to i_a , $i_{L_{a,av}}$ can be simplified to be:

$$i_{L_{a,av}} = \frac{i_a}{d_{buck,a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (3.5)$$

Similarly, when v_{am} is below V_{dc} , module *a* operates in boost mode. In this

	$0 \leq t \leq T/2$	$T/2 \leq t \leq T$
v_a	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t)$	
v_{am}	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}$	
$d_{buck,a}$	V_{dc}/v_{am}	1
$d_{boost,a}$	1	v_{am}/V_{dc}
$i_{La,av}$	$\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)/d_{buck,a}$	$\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)$

TABLE 3.2: Basic equations of the proposed converter for module a

mode, the DC-side half-bridge operates in the switching mode, while the AC-side half-bridge is clamped (with S_{a1} kept ON and S_{a2} kept OFF), as illustrated in Fig. 3.3c. The duty cycle of S_{a3} in this mode, denoted as $d_{boost,a}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{boost,a} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}}{V_{dc}} \quad (3.6)$$

and the command of S_{a4} is the complementary of S_{a3} .

Using (3.5) and given that $d_{buck,a} = 1$ in boost mode, $i_{la,av}$ in boost mode equals:

$$i_{La,av} = i_a = \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) \quad (3.7)$$

The key operational differences between the 3-W and 4-W topologies are as follows. Firstly, in the 4-W topology, each module has its current return path through the neutral wire, resulting in fully independent operation of the three modules. This enhances the converter's flexibility under unbalanced conditions and improves reliability during single-phase faults, as will be demonstrated in the following sections. Secondly, the period of the buck and boost mode differs. In the 4-W topology, the fundamental period of the AC grid frequency T is equally divided between the buck and boost modes. Each module operates in the buck mode when its phase voltage is greater than zero and switches to the boost mode when its phase voltage is less than zero. In contrast, the duration of the buck and boost modes in the 3-W topology depends on both V_{dc} and V_{off} . The basic equations for phase a of the 4-W modular converter are summarized in Table 3.2. Additionally, the key waveforms are plotted in Fig. 3.4.

FIGURE 3.4: Basic waveforms of the four-wire modular converter

The performance of the 3-W topology has been thoroughly evaluated in previous studies. In [74], the 3-W topology is compared to single-stage buck-type converters, and in [98], it has been evaluated against two-stage converters. Both studies demonstrated the superior performance of the 3-W topology not only in terms of efficiency but also in overall size and power density. These findings can be extended to the 4-W topology, as it exhibits almost the same performance as the 3-W topology for the selected case study at balanced conditions.

An additional incentive for employing the proposed converter is related to its fixed CMV. Despite ongoing efforts to mitigate CMV through modifications in power converter modulation techniques, the generation of a high-frequency CMV component persists [87,88,99]. This CMV presents a potential threat to overall MG performance by inducing leakage current through the parasitic capacitance of PV panels to ground and causing electromagnetic interference in the high-frequency range [99]. In the proposed topology, denoted as v_{nm} , the CMV is fixed and equals

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated power	P_r	7 kW
AC line voltage	V_{ll}	400 V
Line frequency	f	50 Hz
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Output voltage	V_{dc}	400 V

TABLE 3.3: Specifications utilized in converters evaluation

V_{DC} . Consequently, the leakage current flowing through parasitic capacitances is minimized, contributing to enhanced performance.

3.3 Topology Evaluation

In this section, a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed converter is presented, comparing it to the four-leg VSC with a cascaded buck converter (4-leg VSC + buck). The 4-leg VSC + buck is chosen from the topologies discussed in Table 3.1 due to its resemblance to the proposed converter as a non-isolated 4-W 2L converter. This evaluation aims to emphasize the advantages of adopting a single-stage power conversion in terms of minimizing losses and size compared to the two-stage solutions.

The comprehensive assessment of the power converters encompasses semiconductor device stresses, losses, and the overall chip area. Furthermore, an estimation of the total volume of magnetic elements in both converters is provided, taking into account main inductors and input EMI filter inductors designed to meet the CISPR 11 Class B EMI standard. The specifications and ratings guiding this evaluation are summarized in Table 3.3. The chosen power rating of 7 kW is tailored for small-scale residential and commercial applications.

3.3.1 Semiconductor Devices Evaluation

The evaluation of semiconductor devices begins by assessing their voltage stresses. In the case of the 4-leg VSC + buck, all devices experience a voltage stress equal to the intermediate DC-link voltage (800 V according to [81]). Consequently, 1200 V SiC devices are chosen. On the other hand, for the proposed converter, the AC-side half-bridges handle voltages with a peak value of $\hat{V}_m + V_{dc}$ (725 V), while the DC-side boost half-bridges are subjected to the DC MG voltage (400 V). Therefore,

1200 V and 650 V SiC devices are selected for AC-side and DC-side half-bridges, respectively. The CoolSiC discrete MOSFETs from Infineon are then employed in the evaluation. To assess the chip area of the devices, it is assumed that the specific on-resistance $R_{ds,sp}$, representing the on-state resistance per unit area of SiC MOSFET, remains constant for all devices with the same voltage rating. Specifically, it is set at $200 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{mm}^2$ and $350 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{mm}^2$ for the 650 V and 1200 V devices, respectively [100, 101].

The selection criterion for SiC devices is to achieve the lowest chip area. Therefore, starting from the devices with the highest on-resistance R_{ds} , the junction temperature of each device is calculated using PLECS thermal modeling simulations. The device is chosen if its junction temperature is below 120°C ; otherwise, the device with a lower R_{ds} is selected until the temperature criterion is met.

Fig. 3.5 summarizes the outcomes of the semiconductor devices evaluation, encompassing voltage and current stresses, semiconductor losses, along with the total chip area for each converter. The proposed converter exhibits higher conduction losses P_{cond} due to relatively higher current stresses compared to 4-leg VSC + buck. However, the proposed converter achieves significantly lower switching losses P_{sw} due to reduced voltage stresses and the fact that not all devices are continuously commutating. This is in contrast to 4-leg VSC + buck, where all devices continuously commute at the intermediate DC-link voltage. Overall, the proposed converter exhibits lower total semiconductor losses with 118.6 W at rated power compared to 134.8 W losses of the 4-leg VSC + buck at rated power.

Additionally, the evaluation of the total chip area reveals that, despite the 4-leg VSC + buck featuring a lower number of semiconductor devices (10 devices compared to 12 devices in the proposed converter), the difference in the total chip area between both converters is minor, with only a 5% increment in the proposed converter. It is noteworthy that the theoretical limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 1200 V SiC devices is four times the limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 650 V SiC devices [101]. Therefore, advancements in SiC device manufacturing, pushing towards the theoretical limits, have the potential to positively influence the assessment outcomes in favor of the proposed converter.

FIGURE 3.5: Comparison of the proposed converter with the 4-leg VSC + buck in terms of semiconductor and magnetic devices.

3.3.2 Magnetic Elements Evaluation

The magnetic components' volume of both converters is evaluated, taking into account the main converter inductors and the EMI filter inductors. The 4-leg VSC + buck includes five main inductors, four in the VSC stage and one for the buck stage. The inductance value of VSC inductors directly influences total harmonic distortion (THD) and the resulting high-frequency noise generated by the switching ripple current [102, 103]. Consequently, the maximum peak-to-peak ripple current $\Delta I_{L,ppk}$ should be limited, and it is chosen herein to be equal to 25% of the peak grid current, resulting in four 330 μH -inductors. For the buck inductor, $\Delta I_{L,ppk}$ is set to be 60% to allow for minimized inductor volume, resulting in a 300 μH -inductor.

On the other hand, the proposed converter includes only three main inductors. A minimum limit for the inductor value is defined to restrict the peak RMS value of the high-frequency ripple current $I_{hf_{\text{RMS}}}$ in both buck and boost modes to the same value [104]. For the presented case study, the minimum limit for inductance is set at 100 μH . To limit peak switching current and core losses, the inductance is chosen to be 190 μH , allowing for a $\Delta I_{L,ppk}$ of 60%.

The EMI filter is designed to comply with the CISPR 11 Class B EMI standard, which specifies electromagnetic emission requirements for equipment in residential areas to prevent interference. The design process for the EMI filter involves the following steps:

- The high-frequency emissions of both converters are assessed by first calculating $I_{hf_{\text{RMS}}}$ at the first switching harmonic that exceeds 150 kHz, a frequency falling within the EMI standard limit.
- Subsequently, the noise emissions are calculated in $\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$, taking into account a 50 Ω line impedance stabilization network (LISN).
- The calculation of the required attenuation by the EMI filter involves subtracting the specified noise limit at the switching harmonic from the calculated emissions. An additional margin should be considered to ensure compliance with the standard, typically adopting a 10 $\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$ margin.
- Given the required attenuation by the filter and considering a multi-stage LC filter, the product of filter inductance and capacitance can be calculated using the methodology presented in [105].

- Finally, by designing the total filter capacitance to limit its reactive power consumption to 5% of P_r , the filter inductance is calculated.

In order to estimate the inductor volume, the simplified methodology presented in [98] is adopted. The estimated total inductors' volume of both converters is illustrated in Fig. 4.11. In addition to the lower number of total inductors, the proposed converter yields a significantly lower inductors' volume amounting to only 78% of the 4-leg VSC + buck inductors' volume.

In addition to the reduced volume of magnetic elements in the proposed topology, it also eliminates the need for an intermediate DC-link capacitor due to its single-stage operation. In a two-stage converter like the 4-leg VSC + buck, bulky electrolytic or film capacitors are employed to smooth the DC-link voltage while being subjected to the high DC-link voltage and the high capacitor ripple current [106, 107]. The elimination of the intermediate DC-link capacitor in the proposed converter contributes to a potentially improved power density compared to two-stage converters such as the 4-leg VSC + buck.

3.4 Control and Modulation

Aiming to ensure resilient and reliable operation of the hybrid MG, various control objectives are commonly categorized in a hierarchical control architecture into three different layers: primary, secondary, and tertiary [108]. The primary control layer focuses on achieving fast load sharing among RES, ESS, and ILCs. The secondary control layer is responsible for enhancing power quality, recovering the frequency and voltage deviation in the MG caused by primary level regulation errors. It also handles the resynchronization of the MG to the utility grid [109]. Lastly, the tertiary control layer aims at achieving optimal energy management, serving as a centralized function in the MG controller. Since the primary control layer handles the power balancing between generation and consumption which is the main function of the ILC, the primary control will be discussed in this section along with the inner control loops of the proposed converter.

The primary control approaches can be categorized into centralized and decentralized control [110]. In centralized control, power balancing in the MG is achieved through a master–slave control approach. On the other hand, decentralized control relies on a droop control approach. The droop control strategy presents several advantages compared to master-slave control, such as increased reliability with

FIGURE 3.6: Block diagram of the control structure for the proposed converter

a prompt response to load changes, reduced communication and computational burden, and enhanced flexibility that allows for easy expandability [29].

In this section, the control of the proposed converter is presented in Fig. 3.6 for two distinctive operating modes: the grid-following (GFL) mode and the islanded mode. The aim of this section is to highlight the converter control structure in both modes and demonstrate the converter's capabilities during balanced and unbalanced conditions.

3.4.1 Grid-following Mode

The control structure of the proposed topology in GFL mode, depicted in Fig. 3.6a, comprises four main stages: outer power control loop, current control mode selector and synchronization stage, inner current control loops and finally modulators stage.

The outer power control loop is employed to regulate the power transfer between the AC MG and the DC MG. The power reference, denoted as P_{dcref}^* , is determined by the droop controller. In the proposed control structure, considering

the interconnection of the AC MG with the utility grid (as depicted in Fig. 3.1), the DC MG droop control is designed to regulate the DC MG voltage. If the ILC provides grid-supporting functions along with AC MG voltage and frequency regulation, a normalized AC-DC droop can be adopted, as discussed in [69]. With $P_{dc}^* ref$ determined by the DC MG droop control and divided by V_{dc} , the power exchange is controlled by manipulating the DC MG current, denoted as I_{dc} , which is regulated using a PI controller.

The output of the outer power control loop is directed to the current control mode selector and synchronization stage, responsible for generating grid current references for the inner current control loops. Since each module of the converter can be controlled independently, a separate current reference is generated for each module, allowing for flexible operation of the converter under unbalanced conditions. During unbalanced conditions, three current control modes are considered. Firstly, the constant input resistance mode emulates an ohmic behavior for each module, resulting in drawn current being proportional to the measured voltage of each phase. Secondly, the constant input power mode ensures equalized power sharing between modules, causing drawn current from each phase to be inversely proportional to the measured grid voltage. Thirdly, the constant input current mode evenly distributes current between modules regardless of the grid voltage of each phase. By measuring grid voltages and selecting the appropriate mode for current control, the grid current references for the inner current control loops are generated.

Each of the discussed current control modes has its motivations [81]. For the constant resistance mode, since the drawn current of each phase is proportional to its grid voltage, this mode helps restore balanced conditions by drawing less current from the weaker phases with lower voltages and drawing higher current from the other phases. Therefore, this mode is advantageous for the AC MG. Regarding the constant power mode, since each module delivers the same power to the DC MG, power fluctuations and low-frequency voltage ripples are minimized at the DC MG. Therefore, this mode is advantageous for the DC MG. Finally, for the constant current mode, equalized current stresses on semiconductor devices are ensured with zero current flowing in the neutral wire.

For the different current control modes, the amplitude of the generated grid current references is limited to the designed rated value. During unbalanced operation, the modules may handle different powers and currents. While the amplitudes of grid voltages do not exceed the rated values, limiting the grid current reference amplitude ensures that the power losses of each module do not exceed

the designed values, ensuring a safe and reliable operation during both balanced and unbalanced conditions.

The grid current references are then sent to their respective current controllers. In the proposed control structure presented in Fig. 3.6c, the feedback of the grid currents is attained through indirect measurements of the grid currents. Based on (3.5) and considering phase a as an example, i_a can be calculated by multiplying $i_{L_{a,av}}$ by $d_{buck,a}$. This indirect measurement method ensures the regulation of both grid and inductor currents without the need for additional cascaded loops. The grid currents are regulated using a PI controller.

Achieving a robust operation of the ILCs hinges on key factors such as precise tuning of controllers for prompt responses, minimal overshoot, and reduced steady-state error [29, 111]. Additionally, the design of the synchronization stage plays a pivotal role, ensuring sustained synchronization during transient conditions and effective rejection of noise and disturbances in the grid signal [112].

The current controllers are then connected to their respective modulators. The modulators are designed to prevent simultaneous modulation of the half-bridges in the modules, as discussed in references [59, 104]. For instance, in the case of module a during buck mode ($v_{am} > V_{dc}$), the modulator of the boost half-bridge, illustrated in Fig. 3.6c, saturates to unity causing its corresponding half-bridge to be clamped, while the buck half-bridge is modulated. Similarly, during boost mode ($v_{am} < V_{dc}$), the modulator of the buck half-bridge saturates to unity while the boost half-bridge is modulated, and the corresponding buck half-bridge is clamped.

3.4.2 Islanded Mode

In the islanded mode, the converter is controlled to function as a voltage source, capable of providing a stable voltage for both three-phase and single-phase loads. The control structure for the islanded mode, as illustrated in Fig. 3.6b, employs reference values for both the peak value of the AC voltage $\hat{V}_{m\ ref}^*$ and the AC voltage frequency w_{ref}^* to generate desired sinusoidal references for the AC phase voltages $v_{x\ ref}^*$. The reference values for the input module voltages $v_{xm\ ref}^*$ are then obtained by adding V_{dc} to $v_{x\ ref}^*$. Subsequently, the generated $v_{xm\ ref}^*$ are connected to their respective voltage controllers and modulators. Similar to the current controller in the GFL mode, the voltage controller is implemented using a PI controller.

FIGURE 3.7: Simulation results for balanced conditions

3.5 Simulation Results

The performance of the converter is studied and evaluated through simulations and experimental validation under various conditions, including balanced AC grid voltages, unbalanced grid voltages, and single-phase/module faults. All tests are conducted at the rated voltages of the AC and DC sides, with a rated power P_r of 7 kW. The converter's specifications are summarized in Table 3.3.

3.5.1 Balanced AC Grid Conditions

Under balanced grid voltage conditions, the converter waveforms at steady state for both rectification and inversion modes at rated power are displayed in Fig. 3.7. As is evident from the simulation results, the converter achieves a pure sinusoidal mains current in both modes.

FIGURE 3.8: Different current control strategies under unbalanced conditions

3.5.2 Unbalanced AC Grid Conditions

Under unbalanced grid voltage conditions, a performance study is conducted assuming the RMS values of the phase voltages v_a , v_b , and v_c to be 190 V, 230 V, and 210 V, respectively. Three different current control modes are implemented: constant input resistance mode (CR mode), constant input current mode (CI mode), and constant input power mode (CP mode).

In the constant input resistance mode, the converter's modules are regulated to exhibit ohmic behavior, resulting in grid currents that vary in proportion to the grid voltages. The constant input current mode showcases the converter's ability to control the modules to achieve equalized current distribution among the three modules. Finally, in the constant input power mode, the converter's modules are controlled to ensure equalized power distribution among the three modules, effectively minimizing power fluctuations on the DC side. The simulation results under these unbalanced conditions have been visualized in Fig. 3.8.

FIGURE 3.9: fault tolerant operation under one module disconnection

3.5.3 Disconnection of a Single Module

The fault-tolerant operation of the proposed converter is validated in the event of a single module disconnection, which may occur due to protective actions or a single feeder disconnection in the AC grid caused by a single-line fault. Thanks to the independent control of each module, the converter can sustain its operation even when one module is disconnected by redistributing power among the remaining modules.

This fault-tolerant operation is demonstrated in Fig. 3.9. Initially, the converter operates normally with a constant current reference directly fed into the inner current control loop. However, the normal operation is interrupted by the sudden disconnection of module a . Despite this disconnection, the other two modules continue to operate without disruption, allowing the converter to still deliver up to two-thirds of its rated power.

3.5.4 Islanded Operation

3.6 Experimental Results

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed converter, an experimental prototype, as depicted in Fig. 3.10, has been constructed with a rating of 7 kW. The parameters of the prototype are detailed in Table 3.4. Experimental waveforms were captured using an 8-channel oscilloscope and include the AC grid voltages (v_a , v_b , v_c), AC-side voltage of module a (v_{am}), and the AC grid currents (i_a , i_b , i_c ,

FIGURE 3.10: Experimental prototype of the proposed converter

i_n). Additionally, the Dewesoft SIRIUS XHS high-speed data acquisition system is employed to accurately measure the AC grid currents' RMS values, THD, and the prototype's efficiency.

The experimental results are categorized into the following sections: performance under balanced AC grid conditions, performance under unbalanced AC grid conditions, performance when a single module is disconnected, and performance during islanded operation.

3.6.1 Balanced AC Grid Conditions

This section presents experimental waveforms under balanced AC grid conditions in both rectification and inversion modes at steady-state, as well as the transient

	Parameter	Symbol	Value
SiC MOSFET	Part number	IMZ120R030M1H	
	Voltage	V_{DS}	1200 V
	Current	I_D	56 A
Inductor parameters	Inductor	L	190 μ H
	Part number	KoolMu 0079908A7	
	Magnetic path length	MPL	19.6 cm
	Core volume	V_c	43.4 cm ³
	Number of turns	N	80 Turns
	Inductor DC resistance	R_{LDC}	20.3 m Ω
Input filter	Inductor	L_f	50 μ H
	Capacitor	C_f	11.3 μ F

TABLE 3.4: Main components utilized in the experimental prototype

behavior under step variations in the power reference. Additionally, efficiency curves of the experimental prototype are discussed.

The waveforms at rated power in rectification mode are displayed in Fig. 3.11a. In this mode, the AC currents are well-synchronized with the AC voltages, resulting in a measured power factor of greater than 0.99. A minor current is flowing through the neutral wire due to the tracking errors in the PI current controllers. Similarly, the inversion mode at rated power is shown in Fig. 3.11b. As evident from the waveforms, the AC currents exhibit a 180-degree phase shift from the AC voltages. Additionally, the efficiency curve of the prototype is depicted in Fig. 3.11c. The prototype demonstrates a peak efficiency of 98.87%, with an efficiency of 97.66% at the rated output power.

The performance of the proposed control structure is evaluated under power reference variations. Two specific cases are considered: a step change in the output power in rectification mode and a step change in the output power from rectification mode to inversion mode. In Fig. 3.12a, the converter initially operates in rectification mode at 50% of its rated power. A step change is then applied to reach the rated power. The waveforms clearly demonstrate the fast and stable behavior of both i_a and i_{La} , indicating the efficient and reliable operation of the control structure.

Similarly, Fig. 3.12b illustrates the step change from rectification mode to inversion mode. The converter undergoes a transition from 100% of rated power in rectification mode to 100% of rated power in inversion mode. Once again, the waveforms exhibit a stable response, highlighting the effectiveness of the control structure.

3.6.2 Unbalanced AC Grid Conditions

The section evaluates the performance and flexibility of the converter when interfacing the DC MG with unbalanced AC voltages. Unbalances in the AC voltages may arise from uneven loading in the AC MG, such as single-phase residential loads, or single-phase distributed generation, or due to faults in the AC MG. Regardless of the source of the unbalance in the AC MG, this section focuses on the converter's operation under different current control modes. The RMS values of v_a , v_b , and v_c are adjusted to simulate AC voltage unbalance, set to 230 V, 210 V, and 190 V, respectively. Three distinct current control modes are presented for analysis.

FIGURE 3.11: Experimental results under balanced AC grid: (a) Rectification mode at rated power, (b) Inversion mode at rated power, and (c) Efficiency curve of the experimental prototype

First, the constant input resistance mode (Fig. 3.13a) demonstrates the converter's modules being controlled to exhibit ohmic behavior, resulting in grid currents proportional to the grid voltages. Second, the constant input current mode (Fig. 3.13b) showcases the converter's modules being controlled to achieve equalized current sharing among the three modules. Finally, the constant input power mode (Fig. 3.13c) illustrates the converter's modules being controlled to achieve equalized power sharing among the three modules, thereby minimizing power fluctuations on the DC MG.

FIGURE 3.12: Experimental results under balanced AC grid with step changes in the load: (a) Step change in rectification mode from 50% to 100% of rated power, (b) Step change from rectification to inversion mode.

3.6.3 Disconnection of a Single Module

In this section, the fault-tolerant operation of the proposed converter under single-phase faults is verified. The study focuses on the fault-tolerant response in the event of the disconnection of a single module, attributed to potential causes such as semiconductor failure or a single feeder disconnection in the AC MG due to a single-line fault or a tripping of current protection in a single module. Given the independent control capability of each module, the converter demonstrates the capacity to sustain operation even when a single module is disconnected by redistributing power through the remaining modules.

FIGURE 3.13: Experimental waveforms under unbalanced AC grid with different current control techniques: (a) Constant input resistance mode at rated power, (b) Constant input current mode at rated power, and (c) Constant input power mode at rated power

The fault-tolerant operation is demonstrated in Fig. 3.14, where the converter is initially running in normal operation with a constant current reference is directly fed to the inner current control loop. The normal operation is interrupted by a sudden disconnection of module a . Despite the disconnection of module a , the operation of the other two modules remains unaffected, allowing the converter to still deliver up to two-thirds of its rated power.

3.6.4 Islanded Operation

Another valuable feature of the proposed topology is its islanded operation capability. In addition to the demonstrated performance in the previous sections under grid-following mode, the converter can control both the voltage and the

FIGURE 3.14: Experimental waveforms to demonstrate the fault tolerant operation under one module disconnection

frequency of the AC side for both three-phase and single-phase loads. To verify this capability, the AC supply is disconnected and replaced with a three-phase resistive load.

The operation in islanded mode is assessed under two conditions. First, when connected to a balanced resistive load of 29Ω /phase, as shown in Fig. 3.15a. Second, when connected to an unbalanced three-phase load, where the resistance for phase b is changed to 58Ω while the resistances for phases a and c remain at 29Ω , as depicted in Fig. 3.15b.

Based on the demonstrated waveforms, the converter proves its capability to regulate both the voltage and frequency of v_a , v_b , and v_c under both balanced and unbalanced load conditions. In the case of an unbalanced load, the zero-sequence component of the AC current will flow through the neutral wire.

3.7 Conclusion

This chapter introduces a three-phase four-wire buck-type interlinking converter for hybrid ac/dc microgrids, incorporating a single-stage power conversion. The proposed configuration of the converter consists of three four-switch buck-boost modules arranged in a star configuration, where the ac microgrid neutral is directly connected to the positive terminal of the ac microgrid. The inclusion of the neutral wire enables the islanded capability of the hybrid microgrid, ensuring a stable power supply for both single-phase and three-phase ac loads. Notably,

FIGURE 3.15: Experimental waveforms of islanded mode: (a) Balanced load, (b) Unbalanced load

the direct link between the AC microgrid neutral and the positive terminal of the dc microgrid allows for the grounding of both microgrids, a capability previously achievable solely with isolated topologies.

Moreover, the four-wire converters are capable of regulating positive, negative, and zero sequence components, offering flexible control mechanisms during ac voltage imbalances to mitigate their impact and ensure optimal operation. This feature is demonstrated in this article by addressing three current control modes: the constant input resistance mode, which emulates an ohmic behavior for each module and then helps restore balanced conditions; the constant input current mode, which evenly distributes the current between the modules; and the constant input power mode, which minimizes power fluctuations and low-frequency ripples on the dc microgrid side.

Additionally, the converter allows for independent control of the three phases, facilitating fault-tolerant operation as demonstrated in this article under single-phase faults. The converter's performance is comprehensively evaluated through experimental tests conducted on a 7 kW prototype under diverse operating conditions, encompassing balanced and unbalanced ac voltages, single-module disconnection, and islanded operation.

Chapter 4

Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC Systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid

4.1 Introduction and Background

When integrating 400 V dc MG with the European LV three-phase ac grid, which operates at a line-to-line voltage of $400 V_{\text{RMS}}$, buck-type three-phase converters are commonly employed to establish a single-stage power interface [3]. Several optimized buck-type converters have been proposed in the literature to serve as interlinking converters (ILCs), including current source converters (CSCs) in both six-switch and seven-switch configurations [46, 49]. The bidirectional power flow capability for the CSCs can be attained through an inverting link [113]. Additionally, other notable options include the Swiss converter [54], the integrated active filter converter [114], and the Y-converter [97, 115]. Previous studies demonstrated that the Y-converter potentially achieves superior overall performance among buck-type converters [74, 116, 117].

Besides the single-stage buck-type converter, two-stage converters can offer an alternative for interfacing 400 V dc MGs with the LV ac grid [79]. In these two-stage converters, a cascaded connection of either two-level or three-level voltage source converters (VSCs) and a dc-dc step-down converter is employed. While VSCs are renowned for their simple structure, control, and high power density, the two-stage solution is less favorable, as the inclusion of an extra power conversion stage and the necessity for intermediate dc-link capacitors result in a degradation of the overall efficiency and power density of the ILC [98, 117].

FIGURE 4.1: Integration of two dc MGs with the ac grid: (a) Utilizing two-port converters; (b) Utilizing a Multiport converter.

Both isolated and non-isolated converters have been explored in the literature for interfacing the ac grid with the dc MG [29, 118]. To enhance the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface, non-isolated converters are preferred [30], particularly since galvanic isolation is not mandatory according to relevant standards [31, 32].

4.1.1 Multiport Interlinking Converters: Motivations and Structures

The rising popularity of dc MGs in residential and commercial settings, as discussed in [33], has prompted a reassessment of conventional approaches to grid interfacing. Traditionally, each MG would utilize a dedicated ac/dc converter for connection to the grid [29], a practice that often leads to larger system sizes and higher costs. In response to these challenges, multiport converters (MPCs) have emerged as promising and efficient solutions [34, 35, 119]. MPCs offer an effective approach by integrating multiple energy ports into a single hub, thereby providing a more streamlined and potentially cost-effective solutions. Fig. 4.1 depicts the proposed concept of using a single MPC to interface the utility grid with multiple dc MGs.

MPCs offer a multifaceted solution beyond mere cost and size reduction compared to the conventional multi-converter approach. They introduce enhanced flexibility and resilience by enabling direct power exchange between various ports. When utilized to link dc MGs with the ac grid, MPCs empower dc MGs to exchange power directly through the converter, reducing dependence on the utility

grid. This strategic integration opens avenues for optimizing power flow among different energy ports and maximizing the utilization and sharing of RESs and ESSs within the dc MGs, thereby improving the overall performance of the system.

In the literature, various MPCs have been proposed to establish a direct interface between three-phase ac grids and dc systems. These MPCs can be categorized into three groups based on the structure of the converter topology, as illustrated in Fig. 4.2: a) dc-link coupled MPCs, b) magnetically coupled MPCs, and c) modified MPC structures. DC-link coupled MPCs, depicted in Fig. 4.2a, are formed by interconnecting conventional two-port ac-dc and dc-dc converters to a common intermediate dc-link capacitor. This approach has been widely studied in various applications. For instance, in the field of PV generation, dc-link coupled MPCs have been explored to form a modular PV generation system based on a dc bus architecture [120]. Additionally, they have been investigated for the implementation of soft open points (SOPs) in distribution networks, where they enhance flexibility and increase the hosting capacity by integrating RESs and ESSs with distribution feeders in multi-terminal SOPs [121–123]. Furthermore, dc-link coupled MPCs have been utilized for integrating RESs and ESSs into the ac grid [124].

While dc-link coupled MPCs are utilized in various applications, they suffer from significant drawbacks. As the power flow among the ports undergoes a two-stage power conversion, the efficiency of the MPC is potentially degraded. Additionally, the reliance on a common bulky intermediate dc-link capacitor [125], as depicted in Fig. 4.2a, increases the size of the MPC and may introduce reliability concerns [126]. Any failure or degradation of the capacitor can disrupt the operation of the entire converter. Moreover, dc-link voltage regulation may be critical, especially when power fluctuations occur at one of the ports, making prompt and robust control of the dc-link voltage is crucial [121, 127].

Magnetically coupled MPCs, illustrated in Fig. 4.2b, incorporate magnetic coupling elements such as high-frequency (HF) transformers and coupled inductors in the converter topology for the power transfer between the ports. In [128–130], partially-isolated MPCs based on dual three-phase active bridges are introduced in three-port and four-port configurations. Another approach is demonstrated in [131, 132], where an MPC combines a VSC with three-phase or single-phase converters through three HF transformers. A three-phase center-tapped HF transformer is proposed in [133] to connect two VSCs. Coupled inductors are adopted in [134] to develop a three-port inverter, while in [135], a multi-winding HF transformer is utilized to couple ac and dc ports.

FIGURE 4.2: Different MPC structures for interfacing dc systems with the ac grid: (a) dc-coupled MPCs; (b) Magnetically-coupled MPCs; (c) Modified MPC structures.

The incorporation of HF transformers and coupled inductors adds to the overall complexity of the converter topology, necessitating customized and optimized designs [136]. Additionally, the presence of these magnetic components increases the volume of the MPC and introduces additional power losses, leading to reduced overall efficiency and power density of the MPC.

To address the limitations of both the dc-link coupled and magnetically coupled MPCs, modified MPC structures, displayed in Fig. 4.2c, have been developed. These modifications involve transforming two-port converters into MPCs without relying on dc-link capacitors or magnetic coupling. In [137], multilevel inverters

are employed as multisource inverters, adopting classic multilevel inverter structures. However, these MPCs were originally proposed for multisource inverters, and therefore, bidirectional power flow control at all ports is not fully explored, with only limited operating modes considered [138]. Moreover, the power delivered to each port depends on the voltage ratio of the dc ports, limiting their applicability as multiport interlinking converters, especially for interfacing directly with 400 V dc systems [139]. Another MPC converter, based on the two-level VSC, is presented in [140], where each leg is simultaneously used as a buck-boost converter. However, this converter also presents constraints in the power flow and the operating range of output voltage, preventing direct connection to 400 V dc systems.

4.1.2 Proposed Converter

This chapter introduces a single-stage non-isolated MPC, named the multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC), designed to link the three-phase ac grid with 400 V dc MGs. Building upon the Y-converter, renowned for its superior performance as a buck-type ILC [74], the proposed Y-MPC extends its capabilities into a multiport ILC, facilitating direct power exchange between dc MGs. In applications, this enhancement aims to bolster flexibility and resilience, reduce reliance on the ac grid, and optimize the utilization and sharing of RESs and ESSs within the dc MGs. The proposed converter offers several advantages, including single-stage power conversion among different ports, potentially leading to enhanced efficiency and power density. Furthermore, the absence of bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and HF transformers in the proposed topology favors power density and reduces costs. While designed for 400 V dc MGs in this study, the proposed MPC presents buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the dc ports' voltage. This feature provides the flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of dc systems.

The rest of this chapter is structured as follows: Section 4.2 offers a comprehensive discussion on the converter's operation, Section 4.4 includes an evaluation of the proposed converter compared to using two Y-converters to interface the MGs in terms of semiconductor losses. Section 4.5 presents the converter's control structure and modulation techniques, and Section 4.7 showcases the experimental results at various operating conditions.

FIGURE 4.3: A schematic of two-port and multiport Y-converters in a modular form: (a) Two-port Y-converter; (b) The proposed Multiport Y-converter.

4.2 Proposed Multiport Y-converter

4.2.1 Derivation and Operation Principle

The proposed multiport converter topology is derived from the Y-converter, as depicted in Fig. 4.3a, transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multiport structure capable of connecting multiple dc ports to a three-phase ac grid, as illustrated in Fig. 4.3b. Initially, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules [97]. Alternatively, in the proposed converter, each module is expanded into a six-switch dc-dc converter. Considering the structure of a three-port converter, the upgraded design includes a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges, establishing connections to the dc ports. Notably, the configuration is potentially adaptable to additional dc ports by incorporating one boost converter into each module for every extra dc port, thus maintaining scalability.

Similar to the two-port Y-converter, the three modified modules are interconnected at a central point denoted as m , serving as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. Since each module functions as a dc-dc converter, maintaining a non-negative voltage on the ac side of the module ($v_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0$ V) is crucial. To achieve this, an offset voltage is required between the grid's neutral point (n) and (m). A constant offset voltage V_{off} is then applied, which must exceed the peak value of the ac grid phase voltage \hat{V}_m . The ac-side voltages v_{am} ,

FIGURE 4.4: Module a of the proposed converter.

v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be expressed as follows:

$$v_{xm}(t) = v_x(t) + V_{off} = \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off} \quad (4.1)$$

where v_x , with $x = (a, b, c)$, represents the ac grid phase voltages, ω denotes the ac grid frequency in rad/s, and θ_x signifies the respective phase angles of v_x .

Since V_{off} also represents the CMV of the converter, the fixed CMV is an additional advantage of the proposed topology. While CMV can pose a threat to overall system performance by inducing leakage current through parasitic capacitances to ground and causing electromagnetic interference (EMI) in the high-frequency range [99], the fixed CMV in the proposed topology minimizes these issues as the leakage current flowing through parasitic capacitances is significantly reduced.

The analysis of the converter is presented by considering a single module (module a), as depicted in Fig. 4.4, and it similarly applies to the other modules as well. This module consists of the two inductors L_1 and L_2 along with three half-bridges: one on the ac side, labeled as Bu_a , and the others on the dc sides, labeled as Bo_{a1} and Bo_{a2} . Although the main focus of this article is on interfacing 400 V dc systems, the subsequent analysis is generalized for arbitrary values of V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . Additionally, it is assumed that at least one of the dc ports' voltage is lower than the peak of the ac side voltage ($\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$), and V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} . Based on these assumptions, the Bu_a and Bo_{a1} half-bridges are under control, ensuring that only one of them is modulated at any given moment, while the other remains clamped based on the values of v_{am} and V_{dc1} , whereas Bo_{a2} will be modulated continuously.

4.2.2 Analysis and Fundamental Relations

4.2.2.1 Buck Mode

When v_{am} exceeds V_{dc1} , module a operates in buck mode. In this mode, the Bu_a half-bridge switches, while the Bo_{a1} half-bridge is clamped with S_{a3} on and S_{a4} off, as illustrated in Fig. 4.5a. Simultaneously, the Bo_{a2} half-bridge operates with a fixed duty cycle, depending on the ratio between V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . The duty cycles of S_{a1} and S_{a5} , denoted as d_{Bu_a} and $d_{Bo_{a2}}$, respectively, can be calculated using the following equations:

$$d_{Bu_a}(t) = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{am}(t)} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$d_{Bo_{a2}} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (4.3)$$

The ac grid current of phase a , denoted as i_a , is assumed to be pure sinusoidal and in phase with its corresponding phase voltage v_a and then can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_a(t) &= \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) = (\hat{I}_{m1} + \hat{I}_{m2}) \sin(\omega t) \\ &= \left(\frac{2P_{dc1}}{3\hat{V}_m} + \frac{2P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m} \right) \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

where P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} represent the power delivered to dc ports 1 and 2, respectively, while \hat{I}_m denotes the peak phase current. Additionally, \hat{I}_{m1} and \hat{I}_{m2} signify the equivalent reference peak phase current solely due to the power of dc MG#1 and #2, respectively.

The summation of average inductor currents (i.e., $i_{La1,av} + i_{La2,av}$), denoted as $i_{La,av}$, can be derived by applying Kirchhoff's current law (KCL) at the ac input of the module, as follows:

$$i_{La,av}(t) = i_{La1,av}(t) + i_{La2,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t) - i_{Cf,a}(t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} \quad (4.5)$$

where $i_{Cf,a}$ represents the current through the input capacitor C_f . By neglecting $i_{Cf,a}$, the equation can be simplified as follows:

$$i_{La,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} \quad (4.6)$$

FIGURE 4.5: Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter: (a) Buck mode when $v_{am} > V_{dc1}$; (b) Boost mode when $v_{am} < V_{dc1}$

Using (4.4) and (4.6) , $i_{la1,av}$ and $i_{la2,av}$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_{La1,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}} \\
 i_{La2,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.7}$$

Parameter	Equation	Parameter	Equation
v_x	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)$	v_{xm}	$v_x + V_{off}$
d_{Bu_x}	$\frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{v_{xm}}$	$d_{Bo_{x1}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc1}}$
$d_{Bo_{x2}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc2}}$	$i_{Lx,av}$	$\frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{d_{Bu_x}}$
$i_{Lx1,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc1} \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{3\hat{V}_m d_{Bu_x}}$	$i_{Lx2,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc2} \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{3\hat{V}_m d_{Bu_x}}$

TABLE 4.1: Summary of the basic equations of the proposed converter.

4.2.2.2 Boost Mode

The second mode of operation occurs when v_{am} falls below V_{dc1} . In this mode, module a operates in boost mode. In this mode, the Bo_{a1} half-bridge switches, while the Bu_a half-bridge is clamped with S_{a1} on and S_{a2} off, as depicted in Fig. 4.5b. Simultaneously, the Bo_{a2} half-bridge operates with a time-varying duty cycle. The duty cycles of S_{a3} , denoted as $d_{Bo_{a1}}$, and $d_{Bo_{a2}}$ can be calculated using the following equations:

$$d_{Bo_{a1}}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc1}} \quad (4.8)$$

$$d_{Bo_{a2}}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc2}} \quad (4.9)$$

Using (4.7) and given that $d_{Bu_a} = 1$ in this mode, $i_{La1,av}$ and $i_{La2,av}$ can be determined as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La1,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t) \\ i_{La2,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

The key waveforms for module a of the proposed converter are plotted in Fig. 4.6. Additionally, the basic characteristic equations of the proposed converter are summarized in Table 4.1. These equations are applicable to any values of V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} , including the scenario presented in the analysis (where V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2}) and also when V_{dc1} is higher than V_{dc2} .

FIGURE 4.6: Key waveforms of module a of the proposed converter.

4.3 Topology Evaluation for Wide-range of DC Ports Voltage

The voltage and current stresses of the semiconductor devices of the proposed converter are analyzed in this section [141]. This analysis aids in appropriately sizing and selecting the semiconductor devices. The converter's specifications and ratings are outlined in Table 4.2, assuming the converter's connection to the European low-voltage grid via its AC port and interfacing with two DC ports ranging

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated AC power	$P_{ac,r}$	10 kW
Rated DC power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	5 kW
AC line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	350 –800 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

TABLE 4.2: Parameters of the proposed converter

from 350 V to 800 V. The AC and DC power ratings are selected for residential and commercial applications and are chosen to be 10 kW and 5 kW, respectively.

In addition to the stresses on semiconductor devices, the conduction and switching losses of the devices are presented at rated power for different voltage levels of the DC ports.

4.3.1 Semiconductor devices stresses

4.3.1.1 Voltage stresses

The ac-side buck half-bridges Bu_x process the ac-side voltages $v_{(a,b,c)m}$, respectively. Therefore, the related switches are subjected to a time-varying voltage of maximum value that equals $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. Meanwhile, the DC-side boost half-bridges Bo_{x1} and Bo_{x2} present voltage stress equal to their respective DC port voltage.

4.3.1.2 Current stresses

The RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices at rated power are displayed in Fig. 4.7 using fitted contour plots. As stated in the previous section, the presented analysis assumes that at least one of the DC ports' voltage is lower than $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. In the presented current stresses plot, one of the DC ports is always limited to 600 V, while the other can reach the specified rated DC voltage (i.e., 800 V) which is the same assumption provided in the analysis section.

Considering the current stresses of the Bu_x switches ($S_{(a,b,c)1}, S_{(a,b,c)2}$), the current stresses increase as the DC ports' voltage decreases due to higher values of i_{La1} and i_{La2} in buck mode. Conversely, as the DC ports' voltage increases, the current stresses decrease, especially for $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, where the current stresses at the

FIGURE 4.7: Fitted contour plots illustrating the RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

high voltage limits of the DC ports are four times lower than the current stresses at the low voltage limits.

For the current stresses of the Bo_{x1} and Bo_{x2} switches, as in a typical DC-DC boost converter, the current stresses of the upper switches ($S_{(a,b,c)3}$, $S_{(a,b,c)5}$) increase as their corresponding DC port voltage decreases, while the current stresses of the lower switches ($S_{(a,b,c)4}$, $S_{(a,b,c)6}$) increase as their corresponding DC port voltage increases. It is worth highlighting that the current stresses of $S_{(a,b,c)5}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)6}$ are mirrored with respect to the current stresses of $S_{(a,b,c)3}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)4}$, respectively, due to the symmetric nature of the proposed converter.

4.3.2 Semiconductor devices losses

The semiconductor losses of the proposed converter are evaluated through simulations, considering 1.2 kV SiC MOSFETs. For $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, a SiC MOSFET with nominal on-state resistance of 30 m Ω (IMZ120R030M1H) is selected, while for the other devices, a 60 m Ω SiC MOSFET (IMZ120R060M1H) is chosen.

The fitted contour plots of conduction losses, switching losses, and total semiconductor losses are presented in Fig. 4.8. Conduction losses are maximum at low DC port voltages, primarily due to their significant dependence on the higher current stress of devices $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$. Consequently, the trend of the conduction losses contour plot closely mirrors the contour plot of the current stresses of $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$.

The switching losses of the proposed converter are primarily influenced by two factors: the inductor current, equivalent to the switching current of the devices, which increases at low DC port voltages, and the DC ports' voltage, equivalent to the switching voltage of Bo_{x1} and Bo_{x2} devices. As a result, switching losses are maximum when one of the DC ports' voltage is minimized while the other is maximized.

Finally, the calculated total semiconductor losses for the selected devices range from 100 W to 180 W, constituting 1% to 1.8% of the converter's rated power.

FIGURE 4.8: Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	10 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	5 kW
ac line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
dc MG voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	400 V ($\pm 10\%$)
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

TABLE 4.3: Parameters of the proposed converter.

4.4 Topology Comparison and Evaluation

4.4.1 Evaluation of the Proposed converter against two Y-converters

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of semiconductor losses of the proposed converter compared to the use of two separate Y-converters for integrating the two dc MGs with the ac grid. The objective of this evaluation is to demonstrate the advantages of adopting the proposed Y-MPC in enhancing the efficiency of the power electronic interface between the ac grid and the dc MGs. The specifications and ratings guiding the evaluation are summarized in Table 4.3. The chosen power level for the power exchange of each MG is 5 kW, which is selected for small-scale residential and commercial MGs. Therefore, two Y-converters rated at 5 kW each are adopted, while the Y-MPC is rated at 10 kW. The losses of the inductors L_1 and L_2 are not included in the comparison as both solutions exhibit the same inductor current waveforms, and the same values of inductors are adopted in both solutions [142].

For both the proposed converter and Y-converter, the ac-side half-bridges commute at v_{xm} , which reaches a peak value of $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. Since V_{off} must surpass \hat{V}_m , the peak value is 665 V when V_{off} equals 340 V. Consequently, 1200 V SiC MOSFETs are chosen for the ac-side half-bridges in both converters. On the other hand, the dc-side half-bridges operate at the dc MG voltage (400 V), allowing the use of 650 V SiC MOSFETs for the dc-side devices in both converters.

In this assessment, SiC MOSFETs from Infineon are utilized. For the dc-side half-bridges, 650 V SiC MOSFETs with a nominal on-state resistance R_{ds} of 57 m Ω (IMZA65R057M1H) are selected for both converters. For the ac-side half-bridges, 1200 V SiC MOSFETs with R_{ds} of 40 m Ω and 20 m Ω (IMZA120R040M1H, IMZA120R020M1H) are chosen for the Y-converter and the Y-MPC, respectively.

This selection is based on the higher current stresses endured by the ac-side half-bridges in the Y-MPC, handling double the rated power compared to those in the Y-converter. Additionally, the junction temperature T_j of each device is calculated using PLECS thermal modeling simulations to ensure that the T_j of every device remains below 120°C for all possible operating conditions.

The semiconductor losses of both converters are evaluated using PLECS while P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are swept from -5 kW to 5 kW, covering all possible operating conditions for the proposed case study. The calculated semiconductor losses of both converters are reported in Fig. 4.9. At the rated power in rectification mode (i.e., when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW), the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 113.9 W, while the two Y-converters experience similar losses equal to 110.5 W. Likewise, at the rated power in inversion mode (i.e., when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to -5 kW), the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 119.7 W, while the two Y-converters experience similar losses equal to 117.2 W. Accordingly, both solutions attain almost the same semiconductor losses at rated power in both rectification and inversion modes, with slightly higher losses for the Y-MPC, mainly driven by the increased current stress on the ac-side half-bridges.

Although both converters exhibit similar semiconductor losses at rated power in both rectification and inversion modes, the proposed Y-MPC features significantly reduced losses for most of the operating range, especially at light-load and when the two dc MGs are directly transferring power between themselves. When a dc MG needs to absorb active power while the other MG has an excess of power generation, the Y-MPC enables direct power sharing between the dc MGs, with the ac grid is only responsible for compensating the resultant power difference.

For instance, when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal 5 kW and -5 kW respectively, the Y-MPC allows for direct power transfer from dc MG#1 to dc MG#2 through the dc-side half-bridges, while the ac-side half-bridges do not exchange the power with the ac grid. On the other hand, in the two Y-converters, both ac-side and dc-side half-bridges handle the power, resulting in increased semiconductor losses compared to the Y-MPC. At P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW and -5 kW, the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 66.5 W, while the two Y-converters exhibit total semiconductor losses equal to 115.3 W, showcasing the significant reduction in semiconductor losses gained by the proposed Y-MPC.

The semiconductor losses breakdown for the two Y-converters and the Y-MPC is displayed in Fig. 4.9b and Fig. 4.9d, respectively, with P_{dc1} set to 5 kW and P_{dc2} swept from -5 kW to 5 kW. The losses are categorized into conduction losses of ac-side devices $P_{cond(ac)}$, conduction losses of dc-side devices $P_{cond(dc)}$, switching

FIGURE 4.9: Evaluation of the semiconductor losses using PLECS: (a) For two Y-converters at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (b) Semiconductor losses breakdown of two Y-converters at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2} ; (c) For the proposed converter at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (b) Semiconductor losses breakdown of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2}

losses of ac-side devices $P_{sw(ac)}$, and switching losses of dc-side devices $P_{sw(dc)}$. The breakdown highlights that the reduction in losses is attributed to the decrease in conduction and switching losses of the ac-side devices, achieved by enabling direct power sharing between dc MG#1 and dc MG#2 through the proposed Y-MPC.

The presented evaluations show that the proposed Y-MPC offers superior performance compared to the two Y-converters. This enhanced performance includes a reduction in semiconductor device count from 24 to 18 devices, along with their corresponding driving circuitry. Additionally, it facilitates direct power sharing between the dc MGs, which is beneficial for minimizing dependence on the ac grid

and improving the utilization of energy sources and storage in the dc MGs. Furthermore, this direct power sharing contributes to the improved efficiency of the power electronic interface, as demonstrated in Fig. 4.9a and Fig. 4.9c, where the larger blue area in the Y-MPC semiconductor losses plot indicates reduced losses compared to the two Y-converters across most of the operating range.

4.4.2 Evaluation of the Proposed converter against the DC-link coupled MPC using VSC and IBs

In this section, a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed converter in comparison to the conventional cascaded connection approach is conducted. For this specific application, the conventional approach is represented herein by the cascaded connection of VSC and DC-DC interleaved bucks (IBs) and it will be named herein as VSC+IBs. The section provides a detailed comparison addressing stresses, losses, total chip area of semiconductor devices for both topologies, and estimates the total size of magnetic elements to meet the CISPR 11 Class B EMI standard [143].

4.4.2.1 VSC+IBs

VSC is typically chosen as the interface converter between the three-phase AC grid and the DC systems due to its simple structure, control, and high power density. However, when interfacing the 400 V DC MGs with the European LV AC grid (operating with a line-to-line voltage of $400 V_{\text{RMS}}$), an additional step-down stage is required. This step-down stage is implemented using three-phase IBs to minimize current stresses on the semiconductor devices and reduce the size of the buck stage inductors.

Fig. 4.10a illustrates, in a modular representation, the cascaded connection between the VSC and the three-phase IBs to form MPC. The VSC and IBs are connected to the same DC-link, which is controlled at a fixed voltage V_{link} of 700 V, given that the VSC operates with sinusoidal pulse width modulation. Key waveforms are depicted in Fig. 4.10b, including voltage, AC grid current, and inductor current waveforms.

4.4.2.2 Topology Comparison and Evaluation

In this section, the power converters are evaluated in terms of stresses, losses, the total chip area of semiconductor devices, and the total size of magnetic elements.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated AC power	$P_{ac,r}$	± 10 kW
Rated DC power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	± 5 kW
AC line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	400 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz

TABLE 4.4: Specifications utilized in converters evaluation

For semiconductor devices, the selection criteria are discussed along with the estimation of the corresponding total chip area. The semiconductor is also evaluated using PLECS simulation for the entire power range.

For magnetic elements, a simplified analytical method is presented for magnetic element design and volume estimation to meet the CISPR 11 Class B EMI standard for the AC grid. The specifications and ratings utilized in the evaluation are summarized in Table 4.4. The AC and DC power ratings are selected for residential and commercial applications and are chosen to be ± 10 kW and ± 5 kW, respectively.

4.4.2.3 Semiconductor Devices

The initial step in device selection involves determining their voltage ratings based on the specific stresses encountered in the converter configurations. For the VSC+IBs, where all devices experience a voltage stress equal to the DC-link voltage V_{link} (700 V), 1200 V SiC devices are chosen. In the case of the Y-MPC, the AC-side buck half-bridges handle voltages with a peak value of $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$ (655 V at V_{off} equals 340 V), justifying the use of 1200 V SiC devices. Meanwhile, the DC-side boost half-bridges are subjected to the respective DC port voltage (400 V), allowing the adoption of 650 V SiC devices.

The CoolSiC discrete MOSFETs from Infineon are chosen for the evaluation, with the desired voltage ratings of 1200 V (IMZ120, IMZA120) and 650 V (IMZA65). To assess the chip area of the devices, it is assumed that the specific on-resistance $R_{ds,sp}$ remains constant for all devices with the same voltage rating. Specifically, it is set at $200 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{mm}^2$ and $350 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{mm}^2$ for the 650 V and 1200 V devices, respectively [100, 101].

The selection criterion for the SiC devices is to achieve the lowest overall semiconductor chip area for the converter. Starting from the devices with the highest

Device symbol	VSC+IBs	Y-MPC
$S_{(a,b,c)1}$	IMZA120R040M1H	IMZ120R030M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)2}$	IMZA120R040M1H	IMZ120R060M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)3,5}$	IMZ120R140M1H	IMZA65R057M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)4,6}$	IMZ120R140M1H	IMZA65R107M1H

TABLE 4.5: Selected SiC devices for converters evaluation

FIGURE 4.11: Evaluation of both converters in terms of semiconductor stresses and chip area.

R_{ds} , the junction temperature of each device is calculated using PLECS thermal modeling. The device is selected if its junction temperature is below 125 °C; otherwise, the device with a lower R_{ds} is chosen until the temperature criterion is met. In addition, a thermal resistance is added to the PLECS model to represent the case to heat sink resistance and it is assumed to be equal for all devices and equal to 0.3 K/W. Accordingly, The selected devices for each converter are presented in Table 4.5.

Fig. 4.11 summarizes the evaluation of semiconductor devices for the two converters. It presents the voltage and current stresses, along with the total chip area for each converter. The Y-MPC exhibits a slightly higher total chip area than the VSC+IBs, with only a 2.8% increment. Considering that the theoretical limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 1200 V SiC devices is four times the limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 650 V SiC devices, advancements in SiC devices manufacturing towards the nearly ideal theoretical limits could potentially alter the evaluation results in favor of the Y-MPC.

The semiconductor losses of the converters across the entire power range, evaluated using PLECS simulation, are illustrated in Fig. 4.12. The Y-MPC exhibits higher conduction losses due to relatively higher current stresses compared to VSC+IBs. However, the Y-MPC achieves significantly lower switching losses since

not all devices are continuously commutating. This is in contrast to VSC+IBs, where all devices continuously commute, subjecting them to the V_{link} voltage stress. Overall, semiconductor losses demonstrate that the Y-MPC outperforms VSC+IBs across the entire power range. At rated power in rectification mode, semiconductor losses for Y-MPC and VSC+IBs are 149 W and 172 W, respectively. For rated power in inversion mode, the losses are 164 W for Y-MPC and 173 W for VSC+IBs.

4.4.2.4 Magnetic Elements

The VSC+IBs configuration includes three distinct magnetic elements: the VSC inductance L_{ac} , the IBs inductors $L_{dc(1,2)}$, and the EMI filter inductor L_f . The selection of L_{ac} directly influences the total harmonic distortion (THD) and the resultant high-frequency noise generated by its switching ripple current. Studies recommend allowing for a maximum peak-to-peak ripple current $\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk}$ ranging from 20% to 40% of the peak grid current to limit the peak switching current and high-frequency losses [102]. In this evaluation, $\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk}$ is set to be 40%, aiming to reduce the inductor's volume. Similarly, for $L_{dc(1,2)}$, the peak-to-peak ripple current $\Delta I_{L_{dc},pkpk}$ is set to be 60% for each inductor. The design equations for L_{ac} and $L_{dc(1,2)}$ are as follows:

$$L_{ac} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk} f_{sw}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} V_{ll} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)}{\left(\frac{2}{3} V_{link} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} V_{ll}\right) V_{link}} \quad (4.11)$$

$$L_{dc(1,2)} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{L_{dc(1,2)},pk-pk} f_{sw}} \cdot \frac{V_{dc(1,2)}(V_{link} - V_{dc(1,2)})}{V_{link}} \quad (4.12)$$

In the Y-MPC, the generated high-frequency noise is dependent on the operating mode. In buck mode, the converter exhibits a switched high-frequency current, which is assumed in the following analysis independent of the L_1 and L_2 values. While in boost mode, it exhibits a triangular high-frequency current. The peak RMS value of the high-frequency ripple current in both modes can be calculated

FIGURE 4.12: Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

as follows [104]:

$$I_{hf_{\text{RMS}}} = \begin{cases} \hat{I}_m \sqrt{\frac{\hat{V}_m + V_{\text{off}}}{V_{dc(1,2)}} - 1} & \text{Buck mode} \\ \frac{V_{dc(1,2)}}{8\sqrt{3} L_{1,2} f_{sw}} & \text{Boost mode} \end{cases} \quad (4.13)$$

where \hat{I}_m is the peak grid current.

A minimum limit for L_1 and L_2 can be defined to restrict $I_{hf_{\text{RMS}}}$ in both buck and boost modes to the same value. For the presented case study, the minimum limit for L_1 and L_2 is set at 50 μH . To limit the peak switching current and core losses, L_1 and L_2 are chosen to be 150 μH .

For the EMI filter design, high-frequency emissions are calculated, and accordingly, the required attenuation to meet CISPR 11 Class B is defined, and the passive components are designed. The $I_{hf_{\text{RMS}}}$ at the first switching harmonic that falls into the EMI standard limit (above 150 kHz), denoted as $I_{hf-h_{\text{RMS}}}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$I_{hf-h_{\text{RMS}}} = \begin{cases} \frac{V_{\text{link}}}{8\sqrt{3} L_{ac} f_{sw} n_h^2} & \text{VSC+IBs} \\ \frac{\hat{I}_m}{n_h} \sqrt{\frac{\hat{V}_m + V_{\text{off}}}{V_{dc(1,2)}} - 1} & \text{Y-MPC} \end{cases} \quad (4.14)$$

where n_h is the switching harmonic order (equals to 3 at the selected f_{sw}).

The required attenuation by the EMI filter in dB μV , denoted as ATT , can be determined for both converters as follows:

$$ATT = V_{hf-h_{\text{RMS}}} - V_{\text{CISPR}} + 10 \quad (4.15)$$

where $V_{hf-h_{\text{RMS}}}$ is the noise in dB μV generated from $I_{hf-h_{\text{RMS}}}$ considering a 50 Ω LISN, and V_{CISPR} is the specified noise limit at the switching harmonic in dB μV with an additional margin of 10 dB μV . For a multi-stage LC filter with n_f input filter stages equal to 3, the product of filter inductance L_f and capacitance C_f is calculated as:

$$L_f C_f = \frac{10^{ATT/(20n_f)}}{(2\pi n_h f_{sw})^2} \quad (4.16)$$

FIGURE 4.13: Evaluation of converters in terms of inductors volume.

Finally, L_f can be calculated by selecting the total filter capacitance to limit its reactive power to 5% of $P_{ac,r}$ and then using (4.16) to calculate L_f .

A simple approach to estimate the inductor volume is presented in [98]. The estimated total inductors volume of both converters is illustrated in Fig. 4.13 where the Y-MPC yields a total inductors volume equal to 81% of the VSC+IBs inductors volume.

4.5 Control and Modulation

This section describes the control and modulation schemes devised for the proposed converter. Such schemes were employed in the implemented experimental prototype to collect the results reported in the next Sec. 4.7.

The operation of the converter is determined based on two power references P_{dc1}^* and P_{dc2}^* assumed to be assigned to the dc ports. In practical applications, such power references may be adjusted by a dc microgrid controller to achieve desired power balances among the ports or they may vary based on the measured voltage level at the dc ports, in a droop-like control fashion.

Fig. 4.14a displays the overall control organization. The implementation of the several control sub-blocks is provided and discussed in the following by referring to Fig. 4.14b-Fig. 4.14f. Considering Fig. 4.14a, the two power references P_{dc1}^* and P_{dc2}^* are first translated into a power reference P_{ac}^* for the ac port of the converter, which is actually controlled as a current source to ensure a regulated power transfer with desired power factor at the ac port and the exchange of pure sinusoidal currents

FIGURE 4.14: A detailed block diagram illustrating the control structure of the proposed converter: (a) The overall block diagram of the proposed control structure; (b) A detailed description of current controller 1 block; (c) A detailed description of current controller 2 block; (d) A detailed description of Bu_x modulators; (e) A detailed description of Bo_{x1} modulators; and (f) A detailed description of Bo_{x2} modulators.

with the grid connected at the port. A second current controller is employed to regulate the current exchanged at the dc port with higher dc voltage.

By utilizing (4.4), P_{ac}^* is translated into the reference peak phase current, denoted as \hat{I}_m^* , which is subsequently input to the synchronization stage. The synchronization stage is responsible for generating sinusoidal grid current references, denoted as i_x^* , for the grid current control loop, displayed in Fig. 4.14b. The ac grid currents are estimated based on measurements of the inductors' currents: by utilizing (4.6), i_x can be calculated by multiplying $i_{Lx,av}$ by d_{bu_x} . This approach allows the regulation of both the grid and the inductor currents without the need of additional cascaded loops. Subsequently, the reference and feedback currents in the abc frame are controlled by linear regulators in the $\alpha\beta$ frame. The output of the ac grid current controller is directed to the Bu_x modulator and the Bo_{x1} or the Bo_{x2} modulators based on the state of Logic 1 and Logic 2, as indicated in Fig. 4.14a. The logic allows to connect the ac current controller output to the modulator of the dc port with lower voltage. For Logic 1, its input 1 is selected when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , input 2 is selected otherwise. Logic 2 operates complementarily, connecting input 2 to its output when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} or input 1 otherwise.

Parameter	Symbol	Equation
Cross-over frequency	f_c	$\frac{f_{sw}}{15}$
Proportional gain	K_p	$2\pi f_c L$
Integral gain	K_i	$K_p f_c$

TABLE 4.6: Parameters of the PI controllers adopted in the current control loops.

The second current controller in Fig. 4.14a is employed to regulate the power of the dc port with higher voltage. The reference of this controller is determined based on the power reference provided by Logic 2 (i.e., P_{dc2}^* when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , P_{dc1}^* otherwise). Subsequently, the power reference is translated into the equivalent reference peak phase current attributable to the port with higher voltage (i.e., \hat{I}_{m2}^* when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , it is \hat{I}_{m1}^* otherwise). The reference peak current is fed into the synchronization stage to generate the sinusoidal current references for the current controller. The controller, detailed in Fig. 4.14c, employs the reference inductor currents of the dc port with higher voltage, defined using (4.7) and regulates the inductor currents in the abc frame, to prevent circulating currents in the converter. Similar to the ac grid current controllers, the output of the controllers is directed to either Bo_{x1} or Bo_{x2} modulators based on Logic 1 and Logic 2. In the experimental verification, PI controllers were adopted in the current control loops. The specifications of the PI controllers are summarized in Table 4.6, assuming that $L_1 = L_2 = L$.

Finally, Fig. 4.14d, Fig. 4.14e, and Fig. 4.14f display the modulators for Bu_x , Bo_{x1} , and Bo_{x2} , respectively. These modulators are based on the equations for Bu_x , Bo_{x1} , and Bo_{x1} summarized in Table 4.1. For all modulators, the instantaneous minimum value of v_{am} , V_{dc1} , and V_{dc2} is defined. After adding the controllers' action, this value is divided by the corresponding dc-link voltage of the modulator's half-bridges to determine the duty cycle.

4.6 Simulation results

Simulation results of the proposed converter are presented in this section to showcase its performance under different operating conditions. The simulations consider rated AC grid voltage and V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively. Additionally, the power delivered to V_{dc1} (i.e., P_{dc1}) is fixed at 5 kW.

Three different operating conditions are presented in this section. In the first operating condition, demonstrated in Fig. 4.15, P_{dc2} is set to 5 kW, indicating that both DC systems are absorbing power from the AC grid. As evident from the waveforms, these simulation results match the waveforms discussed in the analysis section, exhibiting pure sinusoidal AC grid currents and positive AC module voltages, given that V_{off} is selected to equal 340 V.

In Fig. 4.16, P_{dc2} is set to 0 kW. In this case, power flows only from the AC grid to V_{dc1} , and the average current flowing in the L_2 inductors is controlled to zero, with only a high-frequency ripple current flowing through L_2 .

The third operating condition is displayed in Fig. 4.17 where P_{dc2} is set to -5 kW. In this case, both DC systems are directly exchanging active power through the proposed converter, and hence no active power is drawn from the AC grid. The AC grid currents are minimized, and only the current due to the reactive power drawn by C_f flows.

4.7 Experimental Results

Fig. 4.18 illustrates the experimental prototype of the Y-MPC, serving to validate the converter's operation and confirm the correctness of the presented waveforms. The Y-MPC prototype is constructed by combining six Imperix half-bridge power modules PEB8024 with C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs for the dc-side half-bridges, while the ac-side half-bridges are implemented with UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs featuring lower R_{ds} compared to the dc-side devices due to higher current stresses. Control of the prototype is achieved using two synchronized B-box controllers in a master-slave configuration. Bidirectional ac and dc power supplies are employed to emulate the ac grid and dc MGs. L_1 and L_2 are implemented using 330 μ H inductors, and a single-stage input filter is utilized with $L_f = 1.2$ mH and $C_f = 10$ μ F. The specifications of the SiC devices and passive components utilized are summarized in Table 4.7.

To capture the experimental waveforms, an 8-channel oscilloscope is employed to directly measure and display the quantities: v_a , v_b , v_{am} , i_a , i_b , i_c , i_{La1} , and i_{La2} . The voltage v_c is also displayed and calculated mathematically using the oscilloscope's internal math functions, as the imposed ac voltages are balanced (i.e., $v_c = -v_a - v_b$). Additionally, the Dewesoft SIRIUS XHS high-speed data acquisition system is employed to accurately measure the prototype's efficiency.

FIGURE 4.15: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

Experimental waveforms of the Y-MPC prototype are presented in Fig. 4.19 to showcase its performance under different operating conditions. For the presented operating points, V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 360 V and 400 V, respectively, with the ac grid voltage set to its rated value. Additionally, P_{dc1} is fixed at 3 kW. The first operating point is displayed in Fig. 4.19a, where P_{dc2} equals 3 kW so both MGs are absorbing power from the ac grid. As evident from the waveforms, the ac currents are sinusoidal and well-synchronized with the ac voltages, resulting in a measured power factor equal to 0.99. The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point equal to 94.75%.

The second operating point is presented in Fig. 4.19b, where P_{dc2} is controlled to zero, representing the case when the power balance in dc MG#2 is attained only

FIGURE 4.16: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 0 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

by its RESs, ESSs, and loads. Therefore, in this case, only MG#1 is absorbing power from the ac grid. To ensure zero power delivered to dc MG#2, i_{Lx2} is controlled to have an average low-frequency component set to zero. Therefore, in the presented waveforms, i_{La2} has only the high-frequency ripple component resulting in no power for dc MG#2. The waveform i_{La1} remains the same as in the first operating point due to the fixed value of P_{dc1} . The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point equal to 94.63%.

In the third operating point, depicted in Fig. 4.19c, P_{dc2} is controlled to equal -3 kW. This case represents when dc MG#2 has an excess of power generation, allowing it to meet the power demand of dc MG#1 directly through the Y-MPC, and hence no active power is drawn from the ac grid. In the presented waveforms,

FIGURE 4.17: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to -5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

i_{La2} is inverted with respect to i_{La1} due to the different direction of power flow of the dc MGs. Additionally, as there is no active power drawn from the ac grid, the ac grid currents are minimized, and only the current due to the reactive power drawn by C_f flows. The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point equal to 95.71%.

In the last operating point, shown in Fig. 4.19d, both P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to -3 kW. This case represents when both dc MGs have a surplus power generation that is fed to the ac grid. In the presented waveforms, the ac grid currents are inverted with respect to their corresponding ac voltages, indicating the power flow direction to the ac grid. The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point equal to 94.73%.

FIGURE 4.18: Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter.

	Parameter	Symbol	Value
ac-side SiC MOSFET	Part number	UF4SC120023K4S	
	Voltage	V_{DS}	1200 V
	On-state resistance	R_{DS}	23 m Ω
dc-side SiC MOSFET	Part number	C2M0080120D	
	Voltage	V_{DS}	1200 V
	On-state resistance	R_{DS}	80 m Ω
Inductor parameters	Inductor	L_1, L_2	330 μ H
	Core part number	Fluxsan FS-301026-2	
	Inductor dc resistance	R_{Ldc}	21 m Ω
Input filter	Inductor	L_f	1.2 mH
	Capacitor	C_f	10 μ F

TABLE 4.7: SiC devices and passive components utilized in the experimental prototype.

FIGURE 4.19: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 360 V and 400 V under different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} : (a) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW; (b) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 3 kW and 0 kW, respectively; (c) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 3 kW and -3 kW, respectively; and (d) P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to -3 kW and -3 kW, respectively.

The calculated power loss breakdown for the experimental prototype, with both P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} set to 3 kW, is presented in Fig. 4.20. The losses are categorized as follows: conduction and switching losses of semiconductor devices, denoted as P_{cond} and P_{sw} ; core and copper losses of the main inductors, denoted as $P_{core}(L_1, L_2)$ and $P_{cu}(L_1, L_2)$; and copper losses of the input filter, denoted as $P_{cu}(L_f)$. The calculated losses indicate that total semiconductor losses represent 55.7% of the total losses, while the losses in the main inductors account for 26.1% of the total losses. The term "other losses" includes losses not specifically calculated, such as those in the connections between modules, PCB losses, capacitor losses, etc., as well as the mismatch between the calculated and actual losses.

FIGURE 4.20: Calculated losses breakdown of the experimental prototype at P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW.

The transient behavior of the Y-MPC prototype is examined under various conditions. In Fig. 4.21a, the converter initially operates with P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 3 kW and 0.3 kW, respectively. P_{dc2} is then increased from 0.3 kW to 3 kW while keeping P_{dc1} constant. In Fig. 4.21b, P_{dc2} is decreased from 3 kW to 0.3 kW with P_{dc1} kept constant at 3 kW. In Fig. 4.21c, P_{dc2} is changed from 3 kW to -3 kW with P_{dc1} kept constant at 3 kW, causing P_{ac} to drop from 6 kW to 0 kW. In Fig. 4.21d, P_{dc2} is changed from -0.3 kW to -3 kW with P_{dc1} kept constant at -3 kW. The experimental results illustrate the change in i_{La2} to deliver the required P_{dc2} , while i_{La1} remains unaffected by the change in P_{dc2} , validating the power decoupling feature of the proposed converter and its ability to regulate the power flow to the dc MG#2 without causing a disturbance to the power flow of dc MG#1.

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter presents a single-stage non-isolated MPC for interlinking the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. Adopting an MPC for interlinking the dc MGs with the ac grid facilitates direct power sharing between the dc MGs, minimizing dependence on the ac grid, and improving the utilization of RESs and ESSs in the dc MGs compared to the conventional method of employing dedicated converters for each MG. The key motivations for the proposed converter include its ability to achieve single-stage power conversion among various ports, potentially leading to improved efficiency and power density. Moreover, the absence of bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and HF transformers in the proposed topology contributes

FIGURE 4.21: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the experimental prototype: (a) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} increased from 0.3 kW to 3 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} decreased from 3 kW to 0.3 kW; (c) P_{dc1} equal to 3 kW and P_{dc2} changed from 3 kW to -3 kW; (d) P_{dc1} equal to -3 kW and P_{dc2} changed from -0.3 kW to -3 kW.

to enhanced power density and cost reduction. Additionally the proposed MPC offers buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow across all ports, regardless of the dc ports' voltage, enabling direct interfacing with a broad spectrum of dc systems. The analysis and performance of the converter are thoroughly evaluated through experimental tests conducted under diverse operating conditions.

Chapter 5

Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC Systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid

5.1 Introduction and Background

Interlinking converters (ILCs), connecting dc systems with the utility grid, can be categorized based on power levels into single-phase and three-phase ILCs. When the ILC's power level is limited to a few kilowatts, single-phase ILCs are commonly employed. For these single-phase ILCs, the two-stage approach is typically adopted to minimize the dc-link capacitance [144]. The first stage involves a single-phase bidirectional converter, while the second stage can incorporate either isolated or non-isolated DC-DC converters. Numerous studies have investigated single-phase ILCs, evaluating various combinations of the first and second stage converters in terms of total efficiency, power density, and cost [145].

At higher power levels, three-phase ILCs are commonly used. Several single-stage buck-type converters, such as the current source converter, the Swiss converter, and the Y-converter, have been evaluated [54, 115]. Among these, the Y-converter has shown superior overall performance in terms of both efficiency and power density [74]. Additionally, the literature discusses single-stage voltage source converters that can provide step-down capability by incorporating an extra

FIGURE 5.1: Interfacing two dc systems with the ac grid: (a) Employing two converters - a single-phase and a three-phase bidirectional converter based on the dc microgrid power level; and (b) Employing a multiport converter.

step-down stage. However, this two-stage approach is less favorable, as the additional power conversion stage and the need for intermediate dc-link capacitors reduce the overall efficiency and power density of the ILC.

The growing prevalence of dc systems in residential and commercial applications has prompted a reevaluation of the conventional approach, where a dedicated converter is assigned to each dc system for grid interfacing. This traditional method can result in increased system size and costs. Moreover, the use of single-phase ILCs may contribute to voltage imbalances in the utility grid due to unequalized loading across the three phases. An efficient and promising alternative to address these challenges is the adoption of multiport converters (MPCs) [34, 35]. MPCs consolidate multiple energy ports into a single hub, offering a more streamlined and cost-effective solution. Fig. 5.1 depicts the concept of using a single MPC to interface the utility grid with multiple dc systems.

In this chapter, a non-isolated MPC is proposed to interface the three-phase ac grid with the dc systems. The proposed MPC aims to provide a more compact and efficient power interface by reducing the number of semiconductor devices, passive elements, and EMI filters compared to the multi-converter approach, as presented in Fig. 4.1, while maintaining balanced AC grid currents. The proposed converter features an asymmetric structure, enabling the integration of the lower power dc systems into the three-phase IC with a minimum number of components. The motivations for the proposed converter include its single-stage power conversion among different ports, allowing for potentially enhanced efficiency and power density. Additionally, the proposed MPC features a buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, providing the flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of dc systems.

5.2 Principle of Operation and Analysis

The proposed converter builds upon the Y-converter, as introduced in [97], transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port one capable of connecting multiple dc systems to a three-phase ac grid. In its original form, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules, as demonstrated in Fig. 5.2a. To develop the multiport converter, the four-switch buck-boost converter is expanded into a six-switch buck-boost converter formed with a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges. This can be developed in a symmetric or asymmetric configuration. In the symmetric configuration presented in Fig. 5.2b, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied to the three modules. While in the asymmetric configuration presented in Fig. 5.2c, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied only to one of the modules.

The asymmetric multiport Y-converter, denoted as AY-MPC, offers a reduced structure with a lower number of semiconductor devices and inductors compared to the symmetric multiport Y-converter, denoted as Y-MPC. For the presented case study where the two dc systems have different power levels, the AY-MPC enables the integration of the lower power dc system into the three-phase IC with a minimum number of components, allowing for a simpler structure and a compact size. However, a challenge in the AY-MPC is to maintain balanced ac-grid currents, a topic that will be addressed in this section [146].

In the AY-MPC, similar to the two-port Y-converter, the three modules are interconnected at a central point denoted as m , which functions as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. As each module serves as a dc-dc converter, it is crucial to maintain a non-negative voltage on the ac side of the module ($v_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0$ V). To achieve this, an offset voltage is necessary between grid neutral point n and m . A constant offset voltage (V_{off}) is then applied, which should be higher than the peak value of the ac grid phase voltage (\hat{V}_m). The ac-side voltages v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be mathematically expressed as:

$$v_{xm}(t) = v_x(t) + V_{off} = \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off} \quad (5.1)$$

where v_x , with $x = (a, b, c)$, represents the ac grid phase voltages, ω denotes the ac grid frequency in rad/s, and θ_x signifies the respective phase angles of v_x .

In the AY-MPC, module a comprises two inductors, L_1 and L_2 , along with three half-bridges: one on the ac side, labeled Bu_a , and two on the dc sides, labeled Bo_{a1}

FIGURE 5.2: Different configurations of the modular Y-converter: (a) The two-port Y-converter, (b) The symmetric multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC), and (c) The asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC).

and Bo_{a2} . In contrast, modules b and c each consist of a single inductor, L_1 , and two half-bridges labeled Bu_b and Bo_{b1} for module b , and Bu_c and Bo_{c1} for module c .

In the subsequent analysis, it is assumed that at least one of the dc ports' voltage is lower than the peak of the ac side voltage ($\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$). The AY-MPC operates in two different modes: Mode I, where the high-power port voltage V_{dc1} is lower than the low-power port voltage V_{dc2} , and Mode II, where V_{dc1} is higher than V_{dc2} .

5.2.1 Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)

In this mode, the Bu_x and Bo_{x1} half-bridges are controlled so that only one half-bridge in each module is modulated at any given time, while the other remains

clamped based on the values of v_{xm} and V_{dc1} . Meanwhile, Bo_{a2} is modulated continuously.

In each module, when their ac-side voltage is greater than V_{dc1} , their corresponding Bu_x half-bridge keep switching, while their corresponding Bo_{x1} half-bridge is clamped with S_{x3} on and S_{x4} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{x1} , denoted as d_{bu_x} , the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{bu_x} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{xm}} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off}} \quad (5.2)$$

For the Bo_{a2} half-bridge, it operates with a fixed duty cycle when v_{am} is greater than V_{dc1} , depending on the ratio between V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . The duty cycle of S_{a5} , denoted as $d_{bo_{a2}}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{bo_{a2}} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (5.3)$$

The ac grid currents, denoted as i_x , are assumed to be pure sinusoidal and in phase with its corresponding phase voltages v_x and then can be calculated as follows:

$$i_a = \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) = \frac{2(P_{dc1} + P_{dc2})}{3\hat{V}_m} \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) \quad (5.4)$$

where P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} represent the power delivered to dc port#1 and dc port#2, respectively, and \hat{I}_m denotes the peak phase current.

By applying Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL) at the ac input of each module, the average inductor currents, denoted as $i_{Lx_{av}}$, can be derived. For modules b and c , $i_{Lx_{av}}$ represents the average of their inductor currents, while for module a , it represents the average of the sum of its two inductor currents. The relationship is given by:

$$i_{Lx_{av}} = \frac{i_x - i_{C_{fx}}}{d_{bu_x}} \quad (5.5)$$

where $i_{C_{fx}}$ represents the current through the input capacitor C_f . By neglecting $i_{C_{fx}}$, the equation can be simplified as follows:

$$i_{Lx_{av}} = \frac{i_x}{d_{bu_x}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{d_{bu_x}} \quad (5.6)$$

Similarly, In each module, when their ac-side voltage is lower than V_{dc1} , their corresponding Bo_{x1} half-bridge keep switching, while their corresponding Bu_x half-bridge is clamped with S_{x1} on and S_{x2} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{x3} , denoted as $d_{bo_{x1}}$, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{bo_{x1}} = \frac{v_{xm}}{V_{dc1}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (5.7)$$

For the Bo_{a2} half-bridge, $d_{bo_{a2}}$ can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{bo_{a2}} = \frac{v_{xm}}{V_{dc2}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (5.8)$$

Using (5.6) and given that $d_{bu_x} = 1$, $i_{Lx_{av}}$ can be determined as:

$$i_{Lx_{av}} = i_x = \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) \quad (5.9)$$

The key waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC in Mode I are presented in Fig. 5.3a. As evident from the analysis and waveforms, and given that V_{dc1} , which interconnects with the three modules, is lower than V_{dc2} , the converter exhibits symmetric duty cycles for the Bu_x and Bo_{x1} half-bridges. In fact, the Bu_x and Bo_{x1} half-bridges are modulated similarly to a conventional two-port Y-converter interconnecting the three-phase ac grid with V_{dc1} . However, the Bo_{x2} half-bridge is continuously modulated throughout the entire cycle, with a fixed duty cycle when v_{am} is greater than V_{dc1} , and a time-varying duty cycle when v_{am} is lower than V_{dc1} .

5.2.2 Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)

In this mode, where V_{dc2} is considered to be lower than V_{dc1} , the lower dc port voltage seen by module a is V_{dc2} , while modules b and c are interconnected only with V_{dc1} . Therefore, the Bu_a half-bridge is controlled to step down v_{am} to V_{dc2} when v_{am} exceeds V_{dc2} , unlike in modules b and c , where the Bu_b and Bu_c half-bridges are controlled to step down v_{bm} and v_{cm} , respectively, to V_{dc1} . This difference in operation among the modules leads to an asymmetry in the duty cycles of module a compared to modules b and c . Consequently, and due to the asymmetry present in the modules' operation (unlike in Mode I), the following analysis will address each module and its main relations separately.

FIGURE 5.3: Key waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC in different operating modes: (a) Mode I: when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} and (b) Mode II: when V_{dc1} is greater than V_{dc2} .

For module a , when v_{am} is greater than V_{dc2} , the Bu_a half-bridge will be switching, while the Bo_{a2} half-bridge will be clamped with S_{a5} on and S_{a6} off. To determine d_{bu_a} in this mode, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{bu_a} = \frac{V_{dc2}}{v_{am}} \quad (5.10)$$

For the Bo_{a1} half-bridge, $d_{bo_{a1}}$ can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{bo_{a1}} = \frac{V_{dc2}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (5.11)$$

When v_{am} is lower than V_{dc2} , the Bo_{a1} and Bo_{a2} half-bridges will be switching, while the Bu_a half-bridge will be clamped with S_{a1} on and S_{a2} off. To determine $d_{bo_{a1}}$ and $d_{bo_{a2}}$ in this mode, the following calculations can be applied:

$$d_{bo_{a1}} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (5.12)$$

$$d_{bo_{a2}} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (5.13)$$

For module b , when v_{bm} is greater than V_{dc1} , the Bu_b half-bridge will be switching, while the Bo_{b1} half-bridge will be clamped with S_{b3} on and S_{b4} off. To determine d_{bu_b} in this mode, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{bu_b} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{bm}} \quad (5.14)$$

When v_{bm} is lower than V_{dc1} , the Bo_{b1} half-bridge will be switching, while the Bu_b half-bridge will be clamped with S_{b1} on and S_{b2} off. To determine $d_{bo_{b1}}$ in this mode, the following calculations can be applied:

$$d_{bo_{b1}} = \frac{v_{bm}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (5.15)$$

Similarly, for module c , when v_{cm} is greater than V_{dc1} , the Bu_c half-bridge will be switching, while the Bo_{c1} half-bridge will be clamped with S_{c3} on and S_{c4} off. To determine d_{bu_c} in this mode, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{bu_c} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{cm}} \quad (5.16)$$

When v_{cm} is lower than V_{dc1} , the Bo_{c1} half-bridge will be switching, while the Bu_c half-bridge will be clamped with S_{c1} on and S_{c2} off. To determine $d_{bo_{c1}}$ in this mode, the following calculations can be applied:

$$d_{bo_{c1}} = \frac{v_{cm}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (5.17)$$

The key waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC in Mode II are presented in Fig. 5.3b. As highlighted in the previous analysis, the converter exhibits asymmetric duty cycles for the half-bridges in different modules, leading to asymmetry in the i_{Lx} currents. In addition to the key waveforms, the basic equations of the

Parameter	Equation	Parameter	Equation
v_x	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)$	v_{xm}	$v_x + V_{off}$
d_{Bu_a}	$\frac{\min(v_{am}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{v_{am}}$	$d_{Bo_{a1}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{am}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc1}}$
d_{Bu_b}	$\frac{\min(v_{bm}, V_{dc1})}{v_{bm}}$	$d_{Bo_{b1}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{bm}, V_{dc1})}{V_{dc1}}$
d_{Bu_c}	$\frac{\min(v_{cm}, V_{dc1})}{v_{cm}}$	$d_{Bo_{c1}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{cm}, V_{dc1})}{V_{dc1}}$
$d_{Bo_{a2}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{am}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc2}}$	$i_{Lx_{av}}$	$\frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{d_{Bu_x}}$

TABLE 5.1: Summary of the basic equations of the proposed converter.

proposed converters, applicable to both Mode I and Mode II, are summarized in Table 5.1.

5.3 Minimization of the Low-frequency Voltage Ripples at the DC ports

The AY-MPC offers a reduced structure compared to the Y-MPC, which potentially leads to a more compact and lower-cost power converter, especially when interfacing two dc ports with high and low power levels. However, two challenges arise with the AY-MPC: maintaining balanced ac grid currents given the asymmetric structure, and minimizing low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports. These ripples appear on V_{dc2} due to the single-phase power flow from the ac grid, similar to any typical single-phase rectifier, and on V_{dc1} due to the unbalanced power flow from the ac grid to V_{dc1} across the three modules.

To address both challenges, $i_{La1_{av}}$ and $i_{La2_{av}}$ are controlled to ensure balanced ac grid currents and minimized low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports. To achieve balanced ac grid currents, the sum of $i_{La1_{av}}$ and $i_{La2_{av}}$ is controlled to be equal to $i_{La_{av}}$, as indicated in (5.6). Additionally, a new degree of freedom is introduced: the ability to shape both $i_{La1_{av}}$ and $i_{La2_{av}}$ while ensuring their sum equals $i_{La_{av}}$. This degree of freedom is utilized to minimize the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports.

Theoretically, despite the asymmetric structure, the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports can be effectively eliminated. Assuming a ripple-free dc current

FIGURE 5.4: Different waveforms of $i_{La2_{av}}$ to be analyzed for reducing the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports: (a) original waveform; (b) dc waveform; (c) ideal waveform eliminating the low-frequency voltage ripples; and (d) clamped waveform. The waveforms are not to scale.

at dc port #2, denoted as I_{dc2} , the resulting $i_{La2_{av}}$ is calculated as follows:

$$i_{La2_{av}} = \frac{I_{dc2}}{d_{bo_{a2}}} \quad (5.18)$$

As $d_{bo_{a2}}$ tends to zero when v_a is at its minimum value, shaping $i_{La2_{av}}$ to fully eliminate the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports leads to excessive current stresses on the semiconductor devices and inductors of module a . Although these excessive current stresses can be reduced by increasing V_{off} , the overall performance of the converter will be degraded due to the increased voltage and current stresses across all modules. Therefore, in the following analysis, shaping $i_{La2_{av}}$ to fully eliminate the low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports will not be considered. Instead, three different waveforms of $i_{La2_{av}}$ are analyzed with the aim of minimizing the voltage ripples without significantly increasing the current stresses on the AY-MPC components. These $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms are presented in Fig. 5.4.

The first waveform of $i_{La2_{av}}$ resembles the shape of $i_{La_{av}}$ (also the inductor current of the two-port Y-converter) and will therefore be referred to in the following discussion as the original waveform. The $i_{La2_{av}}$ in this case can be determined as follows:

$$i_{La2_{av}} = \frac{2P_{dc2}}{\hat{V}_m \cdot d_{bu_a}} \sin(\omega t) \quad (5.19)$$

The second waveform of $i_{La2_{av}}$ is a dc waveform, where the magnitude of this

dc waveform is controlled to deliver the required P_{dc2} . Lastly, the third waveform of $i_{La2_{av}}$ modifies the waveform presented in (5.18), which ideally eliminates the voltage ripples, into a clamped waveform where the peak current is limited to a specific value. This waveform will be referred to in the following discussion as the clamped waveform, and the peak value is selected to be equal to the peak of the original waveform presented in (5.19). The $i_{La2_{av}}$ in this case can be determined as follows:

$$i_{La2_{av}} = \min \left(\frac{2P_{dc2}}{\hat{V}_m \cdot \min(d_{bu_a})}, \frac{I_{dc2}}{d_{bo_{a2}}} \right) \quad (5.20)$$

For each $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform, the corresponding $i_{La1_{av}}$ waveform must also be adjusted to maintain balanced ac grid currents. The three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms, along with their respective $i_{La1_{av}}$ waveforms, are shown in Fig. 5.5. In these waveforms, V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively, while P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW and 1 kW, respectively.

To demonstrate the performance of the three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms, the required capacitance at dc port #2, denoted as C_{dc2} , to attain a 10 V peak-to-peak voltage ripple at V_{dc2} is defined using numerical simulations. Fig. 5.6 presents the required C_{dc2} for the three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms, with V_{dc2} ranging from 450 V to 800 V, while V_{dc1} is fixed at 400 V, and P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW and 1 kW, respectively. The results highlight the reduction in C_{dc2} when using the dc or clamped waveform compared to the original waveform. For instance, at V_{dc2} equal to 450 V, the required C_{dc2} values are 3.18 mF, 1.14 mF, and 0.56 mF for the original, dc, and clamped waveforms, respectively. Beside the dependence of the required C_{dc2} on the V_{dc2} , the required C_{dc2} varies linearly with P_{dc2} .

5.4 Simulation Results

Simulation results of the proposed converter are presented in this section to showcase its performance under different operating conditions, where the power delivered to V_{dc1} is fixed for all tests at 6 kW. The simulations are conducted with the rated voltage at the ac port, while the dc MGs are allowed to have up to a 10% voltage deviation from their rated value. Therefore, in the following simulations, V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set equal to 400 V and 440 V, respectively. The converter's specifications are summarized in Table 5.2.

Three different operating conditions are presented in this section. In the first operating condition, demonstrated in Fig. 5.7, the AY-MPC is controlled to deliver no power to V_{dc2} (i.e., P_{dc2} equal to zero). In this case, the converter operates as the

FIGURE 5.5: Different waveforms of i_{La2} and their corresponding i_{La1} to maintain balanced ac grid currents: (a) i_{La2} original waveform; (b) i_{La2} dc waveform; and (c) i_{La2} clamped waveform.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	9 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	6 kW, 3 kW
AC line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	360 V – 440 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	350 μ H

TABLE 5.2: Parameters of the proposed converter

FIGURE 5.6: Required C_{dc2} for the three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms with V_{dc1} is fixed at 400 V, P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW and 1 kW, respectively.

conventional two-port Y-converter with zero average current flowing in L_2 (only a high-frequency ripple current) while i_{La1} , i_{Lb1} , and i_{Lc1} remain symmetric.

In Fig. 5.8, the second operating condition is presented, where P_{dc2} is equal to 1 kW. In this case, i_{La2} is controlled to deliver the required P_{dc2} , while i_{La1} is controlled to maintain balanced ac grid currents. Therefore, i_{La1} , i_{Lb1} , and i_{Lc1} are no longer symmetric, as i_{La1} has a lower amplitude, resulting in a reduced power contribution from module a to P_{dc1} compared to the remaining modules. Despite the asymmetric power flow in the AY-MPC, the ac grid currents remain sinusoidal and balanced, as evident from the simulation results.

Fig. 5.9 illustrates the third operating condition where P_{dc2} is equal to 3 kW, representing 50% of P_{dc1} . In this case, $i_{La1_{av}}$ will be zero to maintain balanced ac grid currents. Here, P_{dc1} is divided equally between module b and module c , while module a delivers only P_{dc2} . Once again as evident from the simulation results, the ac grid currents remain sinusoidal and balanced, despite the asymmetric power flow.

5.5 Experimental Results

Fig. 5.10 illustrates the experimental prototype of the proposed AY-MPC, used to validate the converter's operation and confirm the correctness of the presented waveforms. The AY-MPC prototype can be considered a reduced version of the

FIGURE 5.7: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 0 kW.

Y-MPC prototype shown in Fig. 4.18. The AY-MPC prototype is constructed by combining four Imperix PEB8024 half-bridge power modules with C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs for the dc-side half-bridges (instead of six modules used in the Y-MPC prototype), while the ac-side half-bridges are implemented with UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs, which feature a lower R_{ds} compared to the dc-side devices due to higher current stresses. Control of the prototype is achieved using only one B-box controller, compared to the two B-box controllers used in the Y-MPC prototype. Bidirectional ac and dc power supplies are employed to emulate the ac grid and dc MGs. L_1 and L_2 are implemented using 330 μH inductors, and a single-stage input filter is utilized with $L_f = 1.2$ mH and $C_f = 10$ μF .

To capture the experimental waveforms, an 8-channel oscilloscope is used to

FIGURE 5.8: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 1 kW.

directly measure and display the following quantities: v_a , v_b , v_{am} , i_a , i_b , i_c , i_{La1} , and i_{La2} . The voltage v_c is also shown, being mathematically calculated using the oscilloscope's internal math functions, as the applied ac voltages are balanced (i.e., $v_c = -v_a - v_b$). In addition, the Dewesoft SIRIUS XHS high-speed data acquisition system is employed for precise efficiency measurement of the prototype.

The following experimental results are categorized into three sections: steady-state results, transient results, and efficiency evaluation results. In these sections, the performance is examined in both Mode I and Mode II. Additionally, the converter's performance with the three $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms is demonstrated.

FIGURE 5.9: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 3 kW.

5.5.1 Steady-State Experimental Results

This section presents experimental waveforms to demonstrate the converter's performance in steady-state under various operating modes and i_{La2av} waveforms. Additionally, the results showcase the converter's behavior at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} , providing insights into its steady-state performance under varying power conditions.

FIGURE 5.10: Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter highlighting the implemented ac-side half-bridge modules.

5.5.1.1 Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)

In Mode I, when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , the operating conditions are set as follows: V_{dc1} is maintained at 400 V and V_{dc2} at 500 V, with the ac grid voltage set to its rated value. These conditions serve as baselines for the experimental results presented in Mode I.

Experimental waveforms of the AY-MPC prototype, in Mode I and with the original i_{La2av} waveform, are presented in Fig. 5.11 to showcase its performance under different operating conditions. The first operating point is displayed in Fig. 5.11a, where P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW. As evident from the waveforms, the experimental results match the analysis and simulations, showing pure sinusoidal ac grid currents that are well-synchronized with the ac voltages, resulting in a measured power factor above 0.99. Additionally, despite the asymmetric structure of the proposed converter, the ac currents remain balanced.

The second operating point is displayed in Fig. 5.11b, where P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW. Compared to the first operating point, P_{dc2} is increased from 0.5 kW to 1 kW. Consequently, i_{La2} increases to deliver the required P_{dc2} , while i_{La1} decreases to maintain balanced ac grid currents. Similarly, in the third operating point, presented in Fig. 5.11c, where P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW, as P_{dc1} decreases compared to the previous operating conditions, i_{La1} further decreases to maintain balanced ac grid currents. As demonstrated in the three operating conditions, pure sinusoidal ac grid currents that are well-synchronized with the ac voltages are attained at different power levels.

The experimental waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC, operating in Mode I with the dc i_{La2av} waveform, are presented in Fig. 5.12. The first operating point is shown in Fig. 5.12a, where P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW. The second operating point, displayed in Fig. 5.12b, features P_{dc1} at 3 kW and P_{dc2} at 1 kW. The third operating point, presented in Fig. 5.12c, shows P_{dc1} at 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} at 1 kW. The experimental waveforms demonstrate the effective shaping of both i_{La1} and i_{La2} , which minimizes low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports while maintaining pure sinusoidal and balanced ac grid currents. As evident from the results reported in Fig. 5.11 and Fig. 5.12, the quality of the ac grid currents is not affected by the selected i_{La2av} waveform.

Fig. 5.13 displays the experimental waveforms of the proposed AY-MPC, operating in Mode I with the clamped i_{La2av} waveform. The first operating point is shown in Fig. 5.13a, where P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW. The second operating point, displayed in Fig. 5.13b, features P_{dc1} at 3 kW and P_{dc2} at 1 kW.

FIGURE 5.11: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the original i_{La2av} waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.

The third operating point, presented in Fig. 5.13c, shows P_{dc1} at 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} at 1 kW. The experimental waveforms demonstrate effective shaping of both i_{La1} and i_{La2} , as well as the successful limiting of i_{La2} according to (5.20), preventing excessive currents in module a devices. Once again, as evident from the results reported in Fig. 5.11, Fig. 5.12, and Fig. 5.13, the quality of the ac grid currents remains unaffected by the selected i_{La2av} waveform.

FIGURE 5.12: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the dc i_{La2av} waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.

5.5.1.2 Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)

In Mode II, when V_{dc1} is higher than V_{dc2} , the operating conditions are set as follows: V_{dc1} is maintained at 500 V and V_{dc2} at 400 V, with the ac grid voltage set to its rated value. These conditions serve as baselines for the experimental results presented in Mode II.

Experimental waveforms of the AY-MPC prototype in Mode II, using the original i_{La2av} waveform, are shown in Fig. 5.14. In both presented operating points, V_{dc1} is set to 500 V and V_{dc2} to 400 V. The first operating point, presented in Fig. 5.14a,

FIGURE 5.13: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode I, using the clamped $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW; and (c) P_{dc1} equals 1.6 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.

corresponds to P_{dc1} of 3 kW and P_{dc2} of 0.5 kW. The second operating point, shown in Fig. 5.14b, corresponds to P_{dc1} of 3 kW and P_{dc2} of 1 kW.

The waveforms confirm that the proposed converter operates efficiently in both Mode I and Mode II, with experimental results aligning with analytical and simulation findings. The balanced, pure sinusoidal ac grid currents are synchronized with the ac voltages, delivering a measured power factor exceeding 0.99.

FIGURE 5.14: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter in Mode II, using the original i_{La2av} waveform at different power levels, with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively: (a) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 0.5 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} equals 3 kW and P_{dc2} equals 1 kW.

5.5.2 Transient Experimental Results

This section evaluates the transient behavior of the proposed AY-MPC converter under variations in P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} . The objective is to demonstrate the robustness of the adopted control technique and to provide deeper insights into the converter's performance across different operating modes. By analyzing the converter's response to changes in power levels, the section highlights its stability and ability to maintain high-quality performance during dynamic operating conditions. The results presented will focus on both Mode I and Mode II, showcasing the converter's resilience and fast response to power transients.

5.5.2.1 Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)

The transient behavior of the AY-MPC is examined in Mode I with the original i_{La2av} waveform, where V_{dc1} equals 400 V and V_{dc2} equals 500 V. The transient response is first assessed by varying P_{dc1} while keeping P_{dc2} constant. In Fig. 5.15a, the converter's transient performance is shown as P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW, with P_{dc2} held constant at 0.5 kW. While in Fig. 5.15b, the transient performance is presented for the reverse scenario, where P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW, again with P_{dc2} kept constant at 0.5 kW.

The waveforms demonstrate the smooth transition and the converter's ability to maintain pure sinusoidal ac grid currents, despite both the increase and decrease

FIGURE 5.15: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW.

in P_{dc1} . Additionally, P_{dc2} remains unaffected by the transient changes in P_{dc1} , as evident from the unchanged i_{La2} waveform. This highlights the effective power decoupling between P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} , ensuring stable operation across different power conditions.

To demonstrate the transient response when P_{dc2} is varied while keeping P_{dc1} constant, Fig. 5.16a presents the converter's waveforms during the transient when P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc1} held constant at 3 kW. Additionally, Fig. 5.16b presents the transient performance for the reverse scenario, where P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW, again with P_{dc1} kept constant at 3 kW.

The waveforms again showcase the seamless, stable transition and the converter's ability to maintain pure sinusoidal ac grid currents, despite both the increase and decrease in P_{dc2} . Additionally, the change in i_{La1} to maintain balanced ac grid currents is evident. It is worth highlighting that P_{dc1} remains constant and unaffected by the transient changes in P_{dc2} . Although i_{La1} varies with the change in i_{La2} , modules b and c are controlled to compensate for this variation, ensuring smooth operation.

The transient behavior of the AY-MPC is also examined in Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform. The same conditions as in the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform are applied, with V_{dc1} set to 400 V and V_{dc2} set to 500 V. In Fig. 5.17a, the converter's transient performance is demonstrated as P_{dc1} increases from 1 kW to 3 kW, while P_{dc2} is maintained at 0.5 kW. In Fig. 5.17b, the reverse scenario is presented, where P_{dc1} decreases from 3 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc2} still held constant at 0.5 kW.

FIGURE 5.16: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW.

FIGURE 5.17: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the dc i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW.

FIGURE 5.18: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the dc i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW.

Similarly, the transient performance is assessed when P_{dc2} is varied while keeping P_{dc1} constant. Fig. 5.18a presents the converter's waveforms during the transient when P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc1} held constant at 3 kW. Additionally, Fig. 5.18b shows the transient performance for the reverse scenario, where P_{dc2} decreases from 1 kW to 0.1 kW, with P_{dc1} still kept constant at 3 kW.

Lastly, the transient behavior of the AY-MPC is examined in Mode I with the clamped i_{La2av} waveform. In Fig. 5.19a, the converter's transient performance is demonstrated as P_{dc1} increases from 1 kW to 3 kW, while P_{dc2} is maintained at 0.5 kW. In Fig. 5.19b, the reverse scenario is presented, where P_{dc1} decreases from 3 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc2} still held constant at 0.5 kW.

Fig. 5.20a presents the converter's waveforms during the transient when P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc1} held constant at 3 kW. Additionally, Fig. 5.20b shows the transient performance for the reverse scenario, where P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW, again with P_{dc1} kept constant at 3 kW.

5.5.2.2 Mode II ($V_{dc1} > V_{dc2}$)

The transient behavior of the AY-MPC is analyzed in Mode II with the original i_{La2av} waveform, where V_{dc1} equals 500 V and V_{dc2} equals 400 V. The transient response is first evaluated by varying P_{dc1} while maintaining P_{dc2} constant.

FIGURE 5.19: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the clamped i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW.

FIGURE 5.20: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the clamped i_{La2av} waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW.

FIGURE 5.21: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode II with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 0.5 kW: (a) P_{dc1} is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW; and (b) P_{dc1} is decreased from 3 kW to 1 kW.

In Fig. 5.21a, the converter's transient performance is illustrated as P_{dc1} increases from 1 kW to 3 kW, with P_{dc2} fixed at 0.5 kW. Conversely, Fig. 5.21b shows the transient performance when P_{dc1} decreases from 3 kW to 1 kW, again with P_{dc2} held constant at 0.5 kW.

To demonstrate the transient response when P_{dc2} is varied while P_{dc1} remains constant, Fig. 5.22a displays the converter's waveforms during the transition as P_{dc2} increases from 0.1 kW to 1 kW, with P_{dc1} held steady at 3 kW. Additionally, Fig. 5.22b illustrates the transient performance for the reverse scenario, where P_{dc2} decreases from 1 kW to 0.1 kW, while P_{dc1} remains constant at 3 kW.

5.5.3 Efficiency Evaluation

The prototype efficiency is measured using the Dewesoft SIRIUS XHS high-speed data acquisition system for a wide spectrum of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} . In the following results, P_{dc1} is swept from 0.3 kW to 3 kW with a fixed step of 0.1 kW, and P_{dc2} is swept from 0.25 kW to 1 kW with a fixed step of 0.05 kW. The efficiency measurements are reported as a fitted contour plot at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} .

The efficiency measurements are presented for Mode I with different $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveforms, as well as for Mode II, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the converter's performance across a variety of operating conditions.

FIGURE 5.22: Experimental waveforms illustrating the transient behavior of the proposed converter in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V, and P_{dc1} equals 3 kW: (a) P_{dc2} is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW; and (b) P_{dc2} is decreased from 1 kW to 0.1 kW.

5.5.3.1 Mode I ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)

The efficiency of the prototype is measured when operating in Mode I across different current modes using V_{dc1} of 400 V and V_{dc2} of 500 V.

In Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform, the prototype demonstrated a peak efficiency of 95.36%, achieved at P_{dc1} of 2.1 kW and P_{dc2} of 0.4 kW, as shown in Fig. 5.23. At full load, the converter reached an efficiency of 94.89%.

For Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform, the prototype reached a peak efficiency of 95.29% at P_{dc1} of 2.2 kW and P_{dc2} of 0.3 kW, as illustrated in Fig. 5.24. At full load, the efficiency was measured at 94.25%.

Finally, when operating in Mode I with the clamped $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform, the peak efficiency reached 94.88% at P_{dc1} of 2.3 kW and P_{dc2} of 0.25 kW, as shown in Fig. 5.25. The full load efficiency for this mode was recorded at 93.59%.

To better highlight the efficiency performance of the proposed converter across the three $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveforms, Fig. 5.26 presents the efficiency in Mode I. The efficiency is evaluated across the P_{dc1} range with P_{dc2} equals 1 kW, V_{dc1} equals 400 V, and V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

The results show that the original $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform achieves the highest efficiency for most of the P_{dc1} range, maintaining a nearly flat efficiency curve for P_{dc1} higher than 1.5 kW. The dc $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform exhibits the highest efficiency at light loads (up to P_{dc1} equals 0.92 kW), but closely follows the original $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform for

FIGURE 5.23: Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

FIGURE 5.24: Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the dc $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

FIGURE 5.25: Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode I with the clamped $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 400 V, V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

FIGURE 5.26: Efficiency comparison of the proposed converter in Mode I with different $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveforms. The efficiency is evaluated across a range of P_{dc1} values at P_{dc2} equals 1 kW, V_{dc1} equals 400 V, and V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

higher P_{dc1} values, with a slightly lower efficiency. Lastly, the clamped $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform consistently demonstrates the lowest efficiency across the full P_{dc1} range.

Additionally, Fig. 5.27 presents the efficiency in Mode I across the P_{dc2} range, with P_{dc1} set to 3 kW, V_{dc1} set to 400 V, and V_{dc2} set to 500 V. Once again, the results demonstrate that the original $i_{L2_{av}}$ waveform achieves the highest efficiency throughout the entire P_{dc2} range, maintaining a nearly flat efficiency curve.

FIGURE 5.27: Efficiency comparison of the proposed converter in Mode I with different i_{L2av} waveforms. The efficiency is evaluated across a range of P_{dc2} values at P_{dc1} equals 3 kW, V_{dc1} equals 400 V, and V_{dc2} equals 500 V.

In contrast, the dc i_{L2av} waveform exhibits a lower efficiency compared to the original waveform, with efficiency decreasing from 94.92% at P_{dc2} of 0.25 kW to 94.25% at P_{dc2} of 1 kW. Lastly, the clamped i_{L2av} waveform consistently shows the lowest efficiency across the entire P_{dc2} range, with a drop in efficiency from 94.77% at P_{dc2} of 0.25 kW to 93.57% at P_{dc2} of 1 kW.

5.5.3.2 Mode II ($V_{dc1} < V_{dc2}$)

The efficiency of the prototype when operating in Mode II with the original i_{La2av} waveform, at $V_{dc1} = 500$ V and $V_{dc2} = 400$ V, is reported in Fig. 5.28. In this mode, the prototype demonstrates a peak efficiency of 96.04% at P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 2.3 kW and 0.6 kW, respectively. Additionally, the converter achieves an efficiency of 95.68% at full load.

5.6 Conclusion

This chapter introduces the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter for interfacing the three-phase ac grid with dc systems. Compared to the Multiport Y-converter, the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter features a simplified structure with fewer semiconductor devices and inductors, while maintaining the same key capabilities, such as single-stage power conversion across multiple ports, buck-boost functionality, and bidirectional power flow at all

FIGURE 5.28: Measured prototype efficiency for different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} when operating in Mode II with the original $i_{La2_{av}}$ waveform at V_{dc1} equals 500 V, V_{dc2} equals 400 V.

ports. Challenges associated with the Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter, such as maintaining balanced ac grid currents due to its asymmetric structure and minimizing low-frequency voltage ripples at the dc ports, are addressed with proposed solutions. The performance of the converter is validated through experimental tests under various operating conditions, including steady-state, transient results, and efficiency evaluations.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This dissertation has focused on the development of novel Power Factor Correction (PFC) converter topologies to enhance the interconnection between ac grids and dc microgrids. The primary objective was to propose converter designs that achieve higher efficiency, compactness, flexibility, and reliability for future power systems, particularly in the context of 400 V dc microgrids. Through detailed analysis, design, and experimental validation, several key contributions have been made towards advancing converter technologies that can better interface ac grids with modern dc microgrids.

The key contributions of this research are as follows:

- A comprehensive evaluation of bidirectional single-stage non-isolated buck-type topologies was conducted, comparing the Y-converter, seven-switch converter, and Swiss converter. The Y-converter was shown to offer superior overall performance, with a 10 kW prototype demonstrating peak efficiency of 99.26%.
- A novel three-phase four-wire bidirectional topology, named the Four-wire Y-converter, was proposed. This topology enables islanded operation by incorporating the ac grid's neutral wire, ensuring stable power supply to both single-phase and three-phase ac loads. Experimental results validated its fault-tolerant capabilities and effective performance under balanced and unbalanced ac voltages.

- A single-stage non-isolated multiport converter, named the Multiport Y-converter, was developed to interface the three-phase ac grid with dc microgrids. This topology reduces reliance on the ac grid and enhances power sharing between dc microgrids, improving overall efficiency and power density. The proposed design eliminates the need for bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and transformers, reducing cost and size. The Multiport Y-converter's performance was thoroughly validated through experimental testing, demonstrating superior power sharing and efficiency across a range of dc port voltages from 350 V to 800 V. Comparative analysis with other Y-converter topologies highlighted its benefits in terms of cost, size, and performance.
- An Asymmetric Multiport Y-converter was introduced to offer a more compact solution for interfacing ac grids with multiple dc ports, particularly when interfacing dc ports with differing power levels. The challenges associated with asymmetric design, such as maintaining balanced ac grid currents and minimizing low-frequency voltage ripples, were addressed with proposed solutions. The performance of this converter was validated through experimental tests, including steady-state and transient operations, as well as efficiency evaluations.

In conclusion, the novel converter topologies proposed in this dissertation significantly advance the capabilities of interfacing ac and dc systems. These contributions provide pathways for more efficient, flexible, and scalable power conversion solutions in future hybrid energy systems, especially within the growing framework of 400 V dc microgrids.

6.2 Future work

Several challenges and avenues for future research have emerged during this investigation, with some of these areas already under exploration and testing. Building upon the key contributions of this research, the following future work directions are proposed:

- **Exploration of Novel PWM Techniques for the Proposed Converters:** Further research into different PWM techniques tailored for the proposed converters is needed. Conventional PWM methods for two-port converters can be extended to multiport converters. By evaluating the impact of

these techniques on converter efficiency and ac grid current total harmonic distortion (THD), the optimal PWM technique for enhanced performance can be identified.

- **Utilizing Multi-objective Optimization for Converter Design:** Multi-objective optimization techniques, such as Pareto optimization, can offer valuable insights into trade-offs between key performance metrics, like efficiency and power density. This approach is particularly useful for multiport converters, where balancing efficiency with compact design could yield more practical and cost-effective solutions.
- **Application of Non-linear and Advanced Control Techniques for the Proposed Converters:** Investigating non-linear and advanced control strategies could significantly improve converter performance. By employing techniques like sliding mode control or model predictive control, the converter's stability and dynamic response can be enhanced, ensuring robust operation across a range of conditions.
- **Exploration of Novel Hybrid and Isolated Topologies:** Future work could explore hybrid topologies that combine buck and boost functions, along with isolated topologies [60,61]. These options offer additional flexibility and safety, particularly for applications requiring galvanic isolation between the ac grid and dc microgrid, or when interfacing very LV dc systems like 48 V dc systems, making them suitable for a wide range of applications.

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